

D3.5 Final report on engagement and landscape monitoring, lessons learned

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Abbreviations, Terms, and Acronyms

AI	Artificial Intelligence
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
APHRC	African Population and Health Research Center
ARDC	Australian Research Data Commons
CARE	Collective benefit, Authority control, Responsibility, Ethics principles
CFID	Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework
CODATA	Committee on Data of the International Science Council
Consortium	RDA TIGER project members: RDA AISBL, CODATA, DANS, and the Netherlands eScience Center
DANS	Data Archiving and Networking Services
DMP	Data Management Plan
ERA	European Research Area
ERA-OS	OS-related WIDERA projects
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
EOSC-A	EOSC Association
ERC	European Research Council
ERIC	European Research Infrastructure Consortia
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable principles
FP	Framework Programme
IDW	International Data Week
IGs	Interest Groups
GORC	Global Open Research Commons

GOSC	Global Open Science Cloud
HE	Horizon Europe
IDW	International Data Week
ICRI	International Conference on Research Infrastructures
MAR	Multi Annual Roadmaps
NIH	National Institutes of Health
NTEs	National Tripartite Events
NRENs	National Research and Education Networks
OAEs	Opportunity Area Expert Groups
OS	Open Science
ReSA	Research Software Alliance
RDA	Research Data Alliance
RDA-KB	RDA Knowledge Base
RIs	Research Infrastructures
RSE	Research Software Engineering
RDA TIGER	Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions
RSE	Research Software Engineers
SFT	Short-Format Training
SRIA	Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda
TAB	Technical Advisory Board
TFs	Task Forces
TGs	Task Groups

TRUST	Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology principles
UK	United Kingdom
UNESCO	United National Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation
US	United States of America
WGs	Working Groups
WIDERA	Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area

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Executive Summary

This report is a final update of the work done by Work Package 3 (WP3) of the RDA TIGER project. WP3 supports RDA Working Groups (WGs) by providing insights of the Open Science (OS) landscape, including EOSC and FAIR data activities, to avoid RDA WGs effort duplication and enhance their impact. The WP3 activities include the targeted Landscape Awareness service analyses, based on request of RDA WGs, and the Landscape Monitoring & Engagement, which tracks trends and emerging OS initiatives. The report also highlights the contributions from RDA TIGER Output Services and the lessons learned during the three years project. The final section provides recommendations on strengthening WP3 activities, the resource integration, and the alignment within the OS ecosystem to maximise the value and sustainability of RDA outputs.

1. Introduction

This deliverable presents the final deliverable of the Work Package 3 (WP) Landscape and Engagement of the RDA TIGER project¹. The WP3 is one of the branches of the overall RDA TIGER support service which aims to support the development of Research Data Alliance (RDA) Working Groups (WGs) to leverage and supports the RDA community in the creation of standards and recommendations for the open sharing of research data².

The RDA community is a remarkable collaborative platform that facilitates open data sharing and reuse³. Through its WGs activities, it has demonstrated its effectiveness to deliver widely recognised recommendations within the scientific community, such as the Collective benefit, Authority control, Responsibility, Ethics (CARE)⁴ and Transparency, Responsibility, User focus, Sustainability and Technology (TRUST)^{5,6} principles. One way to ensure that emerging WGs remain well-positioned to address current research and data challenges is to make sure that WG activities are not duplicated.

Thus, the objective of WP3 is to provide RDA WGs with a background understanding of the Open Science (OS) landscape, including activities related to European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and FAIR data, in order to avoid fragmentation of their efforts and to facilitate their implementation within the OS ecosystem. Accordingly, the WP3 activities are divided into two main tasks:

- **Landscape Awareness service:** provide a targeted landscape analysis to support the RDA WGs supported by RDA TIGER to fulfill their mission;
- **Landscape Monitoring & Engagement:** Identify and collect information on the overall OS landscape and monitoring updates.

In this report, we present the two main activities of RDA TIGER WP3 (section 2), followed by recent updates and trends observed throughout the monitoring of the OS landscape (section 3). Section 4 provides an overview of contributions to WP3 by the RDA TIGER ‘Output Services’ (WP4), particularly regarding the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB) progress. Finally, section 5 discusses lessons learned

¹ www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/ (accessed 2025.11.28)

² cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101094406 (accessed 2025.11.28)

³ Research Data Alliance. (2023). RDA Strategic Plan 2024-2028 Sustain / Empower / Innovate (1.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00104>

⁴ Carroll, S. R., Garba, I., Figueroa-Rodríguez, O. L., Holbrook, J., Lovett, R., Materechera, S., Parsons, M., Raseroka, K., Rodriguez-Lonebear, D., Rowe, R., Sara, R., Walker, J. D., Anderson, J., & Hudson, M. (2020). The CARE principles for Indigenous data governance. *Data Science Journal*, 19(1), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.5334/dsj-2020-043>

⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/value_rda/rda-and-trust-principles/ (accessed 2025.11.28)

⁶ Lin, D., Crabtree, J., Dillo, I., Downs, R. R., Edmunds, R., Giaretta, D., De Giusti, M., L’Hours, H., Hugo, W., Jenkyns, R., Khodiyar, V., Martone, M. E., Mokrane, M., Navale, V., Petters, J., Sierman, B., Sokolova, D. V., Stockhause, M., & Westbrook, J. (2020). The TRUST Principles for digital repositories. *Scientific Data*, 7, Article 144. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-020-0486-7>

from the overall WP3 activities over the three years of the projects, and section 6 focuses on the conclusions drawn and future recommendations.

2. WP3 Landscape and Engagement activities

2.1. Landscape Awareness service

The Landscape Awareness service is available on request by WGs supported by RDA TIGER and helps identify initiatives and activities relevant to their topic to fulfil their mission.

A generic methodology for the engagement and landscape analysis has been developed (Figure 1) to systematically identify relevant initiatives and activities according to the specific requests of the WGs, and thus across different ecosystems. The analysis scrutinised RDA and RDA TIGER ecosystem and then extended beyond the RDA TIGER consortium (RDA, DANS, Research Software Alliance (ReSA) and CODATA) to map similar initiatives or potentially interested parties on the WG’s subject, targeting national, European and international initiatives in the field of study.

Figure 1. Generic methodology approach used by the Engagement and Landscape analysis service

This methodology and the sources used are available in an attached dataset⁷, and provide a ready-to-use procedure for any WG member who wishes to conduct a similar study or simply iterate the analysis. The resources collected from the different Landscape Awareness service requested by RDA WGs are attached and available in a dataset⁸). Other initiatives and services that have been reviewed but not shared with the WGs, notably due to the limited relevance, are also shared and attached to this report⁹, in order to facilitate their usability for other potential users.

To fulfil its task, the WP3 Landscape Awareness service needs to have a central role within RDA TIGER services, by interacting with the

- **Facilitation service (WP5)**, by being in liaison with RDA co-chairs through their RDA TIGER Facilitator, who can request the landscape analysis report;

⁷ Molloy, L., & GRAU, N. (2025). RDA TIGER Landscape Analyses datasets [Data set]. Zenodo.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034188>

⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034188>

⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034188>

- **Outputs service (WP4)**, by implementing the gathered resources during the requested landscape analysis service into the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA KB);
- **Communication service (WP2)**, which, by disseminating activities carried out across the different WPs, could be relevant to include into the future landscape analysis reports.

For more details on the role of and scope of the Landscape Awareness service, we recommend consulting the two published deliverables, D3.2¹⁰ and D3.3¹¹, both entitled “Engagement Services Status” .

2.2. Landscape Monitoring & Engagement

WP3 has recognised the rapidly-changing nature and vast scope of the research data sharing landscape. Thus, it is crucial to monitor the evolution of the OS landscape, its development and trends in order to provide up-to-date information to the RDA WGs .

The first task was to set the context for the study of the OS ecosystem and to identify relevant initiatives to include and monitor throughout the three years of the project. The **D3.1-OS Landscape Analysis and Potential Engagement Targets**¹² provides an overview of the methodology behind identifying relevant initiatives by following approaches that are:

- Domain agnostic (section 3.1);
- Domain specific (section 3.2);
- Geographic (national and regional) (section 3.3).

The geographic resources collected during the different iterations of the OS Landscape Analysis were collected in datasets, containing over 200 resources from different infrastructure categories¹³, and countries around the world, divided by geographic region. The resources will be implemented into the RDA-KB Support Materials Drawer, and are available on Zenodo. For more details on the RDA-KB tool and service, D3.1 presents how the RDA-KB has been designed and built, and section 4 provides an up-to-date overview of the service and its features.

At this time of writing, two iterations of the OS Landscape reports have been published:

¹⁰ Rettberg, N., & Asmi, A. (2023). D3.2 Engagement Services Service Update (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10444701>

¹¹ O'Connor, R., Papadopoulou, A., Lehtsalu, L., Halbert, G., & Delipalta, A. (2024). RDA TIGER D3.3 Engagement Services Status. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534784>

¹² Rettberg, N., Asmi, A., Molloy, L., Hugo, W., Delipalta, A., & Saldner, S. (2023). RDA TIGER D3.1 OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

¹³Categories include: National research and education networks (NRENs); Platforms/Services; Training/Education

- **D3.4-Second OS Landscape Analysis and Potential Engagement Targets¹⁴**: published in October 2024, provides an update and extends the ground covered by the earlier D3.1 report;
- **MS10-Updated Landscape Analysis for Project Final Period¹⁵**: published in June 2025, provides an update of the development of the initiatives covered in the two previous reports.

This report represents the final iteration of the OS Landscape analysis and a brief overview of updates and trends.

3. Overview of updates and trends in the OS landscape

In this section, we report updates on initiatives since the previous RDA TIGER report MS10¹⁶ in June 2025. To facilitate understanding of each reviewed initiative, we provide, at the beginning of each section, a brief description of each initiative's scope and activities, followed by a short summary of the trends and evolution of activities since the start of the OS Landscape analysis reports in June 2023¹⁷.

The structure of this report follows that of the first report, D3.1¹⁸, and is maintained throughout the update reports to make it easier to follow the reading of the different iterations. We therefore strongly recommend that the new readers consult the details of the methodology used, as well as the initiatives examined described in report D3.1¹⁹.

3.1. Developments in domain-agnostic initiatives

3.1.1. Within RDA community

In this section, we explore the domain-agnostic activities among the RDA community and report its updates and trends.

The three main activities of RDA explored are:

- **RDA groups^{20,21}**
 - *Interest Groups (IGs)*: serve as a platform of exchange among individuals wishing to explore a shared interest. Endorsed IG remains active as long as they continue to

¹⁴ Molloy, L. (2024). RDA TIGER D3.4 Second OS Landscape analysis and potential engagement targets. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017310>

¹⁵ GRAU, N. (2025). RDA TIGER MS10: Updated Landscape Analysis for Project Final Period. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

¹⁶ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

²⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda-groups/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

²¹ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

contribute to their objectives. IG produces outputs such as surveys, recommendations, reports and can initiate new WG.

- *Working Groups (WGs)*: have a specific function in producing concrete outputs or recommendations on a specific topic. They have a fixed period of time (12-18months) to complete their task. The WG outputs can include technical specification, standards or best practices as well as conceptual model or framework or implemented policies.
- *WGs supported by RDA TIGER*: these are RDA WGs that have benefited from RDA TIGER services such as facilitation, landscape awareness or communication.
- **RDA Output²²**: RDA Outputs and Recommendations have changed in between D3.1 and D3.4, with clearer definitions of an RDA Recommendation and an Output, and how these differ
 - *RDA Recommendations*: are produced by RDA WGs and are the official, endorsed results of the RDA and considered our ‘flagship’ Outputs;
 - *Supporting Outputs*: are useful solutions from RDA WGs, IGs, or CoPs, but may not be as clearly adoptable as RDA Recommendations;
 - *Other Outputs*: are used to describe resources that have been published on the RDA website following a request by a WG, IG or CoP, but have received no level of endorsement. They could include workshop reports, published articles, survey results, etc.
- **RDA Plenary pathways**:
 - *RDA Plenary*: are an important event at which members of the RDA come together with the RDA Plenaries. They are held every six months in different places around the world, alternating between virtual and in person events;
 - *Pathways*: help plenary attendees navigate the plenary programme, to find and attend programme sessions of most relevance and interest. Pathways for each plenary are created and reviewed by RDA’s Technical Advisory Board²³ (TAB)

Summary of domain-agnostic efforts within the RDA community:

- The growth of RDA WGs is higher than RDA IGs over just three years and can come from the fact that RDA WGs often emerged from IGs.
- The number of RDA IGs is more abundant than RDA WGs, and can be partly explained by the lack of requirement for IGs to finish after completion of a specific term, in contrast to RDA WGs which must be completed within 12-18 months.
- The overall distribution between domain-agnostic and domain-specific WGs appears balanced, compared to RDA IGs. This difference can be explained by the more exploratory nature of IGs which offers a broader topics platform of discussion.

²² www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/ (accessed 2025.12.20)

²³ www.rd-alliance.org/technical-advisory-board/ (accessed 2025.12.20)

- The great number of new members who join the RDA community among the RDA WGs supported by RDA TIGER partly indicates the growing interest of the research community for RDA alliance activities.
- The WG Recommendation outputs growth of 25% in a year, indicates the flourishing activity of RDA WGs
- The RDA Plenary pathways indicate a predominance of domain-agnostic sessions. The advent of AI made a significant shift in the nature of the sessions with a surge of AI related-activity.

3.1.1.1. RDA domain-agnostic groups

Table 1 shows the current number of domain-agnostic RDA WGs and IGs, at the time of writing (November 2025).

Table 1. Numbers of domain agnostic RDA WGs and IGs.

	Number of RDA WGs	Number of RDA IGs
Domain agnostic	22 ²⁴	32 ²⁵
Total (categorised)	45 ²⁶	51 ²⁷

Since the previous MS10²⁸ report, published in June 2025, one new WG, Reproducibility checklist WG²⁹ has been created, which has been supported by RDA TIGER since its inception, along with the development of three new IGs:

- Dataspaces in the Research Ecosystem IG³⁰;
- Complex Citation Implementation IG³¹ ;
- Infrastructure for Non-Traditional Research Outputs and Processes IG³²

²⁴www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group&_primary_domain=domain-agnostic (accessed 2025.11.10)

²⁵www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=interest-group&_primary_domain=domain-agnostic (accessed 2025.11.10)

²⁶www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Csocial-sciences%2Cdomain-agnostic%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences

²⁷www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=interest-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences%2Cdomain-agnostic (accessed 2025.11.10)

²⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

²⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-reproducibility-checklist-working-group/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

³⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/dataspaces-in-the-research-ecosystem/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.10)

³¹ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/complex-citation-implementation-interest-group-cci-ig/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.10)

³² www.rd-alliance.org/groups/infrastructure-for-non-traditional-research-outputs-and-processes-infra4ntros/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.10)

Regarding growth of the RDA WGs and IGs over the years, we counted in total 45 RDA WGs and 51 RDA IG, while the previous reports (D3.1³³ and D3.4³⁴) show higher numbers. In fact, D3.1 indicates a total of 47 RDA WGs and 65 IGs, and the D3.4 report gives a total 48 WGs and 61 IGs, against the 45 WGs and 51 IGs counted at the time of writing. The counted 45 RDA WGs and 51 RDA IGs refer to groups categorized as either domain-agnostic or domain-specific, by selecting all the categories of the “Primary domain” filter. However, when the “Primary domain” filter isn’t used, the RDA website indicates a total of 66 WGs³⁵ and 70 IGs³⁶. As the previous reports show a higher number of groups, we can consider that the referring numbers come from unfiltered results. Based on this presumption, we can estimate the evolution of RDA WGs and IGs since 2023, the year of the first D3.1 report, about 40% and 7% respectively.

This growth highlights a remarkable and prolific development of RDA WGs activity over just three years. This tendency can be explained that RDA WGs often emerged from identified issues or as continuation of activities that began in IGs. For example, the WGs supported by RDA TIGER:

- RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption’ WG, from the RDA/WDS Certification of Digital Repositories IG³⁷;
- RDA Reproducibility Checklist WG, form the Reproducibility IG³⁸;
- GORC International Model WG, from Global Open Research Commons IG³⁹

With a total of 51 or 70 IGs, resulting from filtered or unfiltered categories, the IGs appear to be more abundant in number than the 45 filtered or 66 unfiltered WGs. This difference can be explained by the lack of requirement for IGs to finish after completion of a specific term (in contrast, RDA Working Groups must complete substantive activity within 12-18 months).

RDA IGs are more likely to focus on domain-agnostic activities than RDA WGs, with 48% (22 out of 45) domain agnostic RDA WGs and 62% (31 out of 51) domain agnostic IGs. This difference in domain activity between WGs and IGs can be explained by the more exploratory and less constrained nature of IG activities, which provide a discussion platform for broader topics.

Table 2. Domain agnostic RDA WGs supported by RDA TIGER

Date (YY-MM-DD)	RDA WGs name and link
2023-01-01	GORC International Model WG
2023-01-01	National PID Strategies WG
2023-10-12	RDA/CODATA Data Systems, Tools, and Services for Crisis Situations WG

³³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096611>

³⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017309>

³⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?group_type=working-group (accessed 2025.11.13)

³⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?group_type=interest-group (accessed 2025.11.13)

³⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rdawds-certification-digital-repositories-ig/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

³⁸ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/reproducibility-ig/posts/?post=189545 (accessed 2025.11.13)

³⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/global-open-research-commons-ig/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

2023-10-12	RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption WG
2023-10-16	RDA Reproducibility Checklist Working Group
2024-06-01	RDA & ReSA Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software WG (PRO4RS)
2025-01-28	Global Open Research Commons International Implementations Working Group (GORC II WG)
2025-09-24	I-ADOPT WG
2024-02-13	Community-based catalogue of requirements for trustworthy Technical Repository Service Providers Working Group (TRSPs WG)*
2024-07-29	FAIR Mappings WG*
2025-01-20	Mapping the Landscape of Digital Research Tools II WG*
2025-02-11	Common maDMPs API WG*

* indicates WGs' received RDA TIGER support from their inception.

Since the MS10⁴⁰ report in June 2025, no new RDA WGs have received facilitation support from RDA TIGER. However, since its launch in 2023, RDA TIGER has supported in total 12 out of 23 domain-agnostic RDA WGs, and four of them have received RDA TIGER support since their inception (Table 2).

3.1.1.2. RDA domain-agnostic outputs

Since the last MS10⁴¹ report, 3 out of 8 new outputs have been domain-agnostic. Only one WG Recommendations have been released, and was published by a domain-specific WG⁴²(more further details in section 3.2.1.2).

Other domain-agnostic outputs have been published under different categories such as

- Supported Outputs⁴³: “RDA Data Versioning IG Compilation of Data Versioning Use Cases”, published by the Data Versioning IG⁴⁴;
- Other Outputs⁴⁵: “Case studies of implementation of policies that support research software in research organisation” and the “PRO4RS WG Final Report”, both published by RDA TIGER supported group, RDA & ReSA: Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software WG⁴⁶, supported by RDA TIGER.

⁴⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

⁴¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

⁴² www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_start_date=2025-04-29%2C&_end_date=%2C2025-11-04&_sort=date_desc (accessed 2025.11.10)

⁴³ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_output_type=ig-supporting-output&_sort=date_desc (accessed 2025.11.13)

⁴⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/data-versioning-ig/outputs/?output=195455 (accessed 2025.11.13)

⁴⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_output_type=working-group-other-output&_sort=date_desc (accessed 2025.11.13)

⁴⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-resa-policies-research-organisations-research-software-pro4rs/outputs/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

At the time of writing, a total of 156 RDA Outputs and Recommendations are published online⁴⁷, which represents an increase of almost 29% since the D3.4⁴⁸ report in 2024 which counts 121 numbers of outputs.

The highest-priority category of RDA outputs is WG Recommendations, which are officially reviewed and endorsed. This category currently includes 45 publications⁴⁹, representing a growth of 25% since the D3.4 report (with 34 Recommendations)⁵⁰. This one year growth indicates the flourishing activity of RDA WGs.

3.1.1.3. RDA Plenary Pathways

Table 3 shows the RDA themes and pathways presented at the different RDA Plenaries, since the first D3.1⁵¹ RDA TIGER landscape analysis report in June 2023. Four RDA Plenary have taken place, with two being in-person events; RDA P23 in Costa Rica and RDA P25 in Australia⁵².

The RDA Plenaries pathways mainly focus on domain-agnostic discipline, with only one (for RDA P22, P24 and P25) or two discipline focus pathways (for RDA P21 and P23) (Table 3). This pattern underscores the predominantly domain-agnostic orientation of these events which are more likely to apply to all (e.g. FAIR principles).

Each RDA Plenary is held under a specific theme, providing thematic guidance for the plenary pathways and sessions. Before the RDA TIGER activities start in 2023, previous themes seem to promote OS practices and the impact of data for addressing global challenges, with the RDA P19 theme on “Data To Improve Our World”, RDA P17 on “Opening data for global challenges” and the RDA P11 on “From Big Data to Open Data: Mobilizing the Data Revolution”⁵³.

⁴⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_sort=date_desc (accessed 2025.11.28)

⁴⁸ <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017310>

⁴⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_output_type=working-group-recommendation&_sort=date_desc (accessed 2025.11.13)

⁵⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017309>

⁵¹ <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

⁵² www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

⁵³ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/>

Table 3. Overview of RDA theme and pathways presented at the RDA Plenary, since RDA TIGER activities starts in 2023.

Year	2023	2024		2025	
RDA Plenary	P21 ⁵⁴	P22 ⁵⁵	P23 ⁵⁶	P24 ⁵⁷	P25 ⁵⁸
Theme ⁵⁹	A Festival of Data	Local Action - Global Connection	Sustainable Science	Data for Emerging Technologies	Data for Positive Change: Empowering Communities and Advancing Research
Number of Pathways	11	8	10	9	9
Names of the Pathways	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Principles	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Principles	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Adoption	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Adoption and Implementation	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Adoption and Implementation
	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Adoption	Data Infrastructures and Environments	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Implementation	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Evaluation and Policy	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Evaluation and Policy
	Data Infrastructures and Environments - Institutional	Training, Stewardship, and Data Management Planning	FAIR, CARE, TRUST – Evaluation and Policy	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Generalist	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Generalist

⁵⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/idw-2023-p21/ (accessed 2025.12.18)

⁵⁵ archive.rd-alliance.org/rdas-22nd-plenary-pathways-programme-navigation/ and www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-23rd-plenary-meeting-san-jose-costa-rica/ (accessed 2025.11.10)

⁵⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Pathways-P23-filtered.docx-3.pdf (accessed 2025.11.10)

⁵⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/rda-p24/pathways/ (accessed 2025.11.10)

⁵⁸ www.rd-alliance.org/rda-p25-timeline/p25-call-for-session/ (accessed 2025.11.10)

⁵⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

	Data Infrastructures and Environments - Regional or Disciplinary*	Semantics, Ontology, Standardisation	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Generalist	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Discipline Focused*	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Discipline Focused*
	Data Infrastructures and Environments - International	Data Lifecycles – Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward	Data Infrastructures and Environments – Discipline Aligned*	Training, Stewardship, and Data Management Planning	Training, Stewardship, and Data Management Planning
	Training, Stewardship, and Data Management Planning	Discipline Focused Data Issues*	Training, Stewardship skill, and Data Management Planning	Semantics, Ontology, and Standardisation	Semantics, Ontology, and Standardisation
	Semantics, Ontology, Standardisation	Research Software	Semantics, Ontology, and Standardization	Data Lifecycles – Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward	Data Lifecycles – Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward
	Data Lifecycles - Versioning, Provenance, Citation, and Reward	Other	Data Lifecycles – Versioning, Provenance, Citation, Reward, and Preservation	AI meets data: exploring use cases, applications and innovation	AI meets data: exploring use cases, applications and innovation
	Discipline Focused Data Issues*		Discipline-Focused Sessions*	Other	Other
	Research Software		Other		
	Other				

* Indicates domain specific pathways.

The RDA P21, P22 and P23 continue to focus on the importance of data and its impact into society and the research community with

- RDA P21 showcasing the flourishing world of data with the theme “A Festival of Data”;
- RDA P22 recognising the importance of data inclusiveness with the “Local Action - Global Connection” theme;
- RDA P23 focusing on data reliability with the “Sustainable Science” theme.

The RDA P24 reveals a shift in topic direction with the “Data for Emerging Technologies” theme highlighting the impact of AI or Large Language Model (LLM) on data and among the research community. The creation of a new pathway “AI meets data: exploring use cases, applications and innovation” gathered in total seven sessions (19%) reflects “a rapid advancement in AI technologies”⁶⁰.

Reports of each Plenary are provided by TAB. The reports confirm the constant crucial place of domain-agnostic disciplines, especially the FAIR, CARE and TRUST pathways as a core of RDA activity (RDA P21⁶¹, P22⁶², P23⁶³ and P24⁶⁴:). Reports also highlight the impact of AI into the nature of the sessions, especially in AI related-sessions like the surge of the Semantic, Ontology and Standardisation pathways notified in the RDA P25 report⁶⁵.

The upcoming RDA P26⁶⁶ is scheduled for March 16-20, 2026; under the theme: Data Continuity for Research Resilience, however the pathways have not yet been announced.

3.1.2. Within EOSC ecosystem

In this section, we explore the domain-agnostic activities among the EOSC ecosystem and report its updates and trends.

The four main activities of EOSC ecosystem are explored:

- EOSC implementation related
 - **Horizon Europe projects:**
 - *INFRAEOSC projects*: serves the EOSC ambition of contributing to a Web of FAIR research data where researchers and innovators can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research and innovation.
 - *OS related ERA projects*: serves the EOSC and OS related Priority Area of the European Research Area Policy Agenda.

⁶⁰ https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/TAB-Report-VP24_FINAL.pdf

⁶¹ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/idw-2023-p21/highlights-p21/>

⁶² https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/TAB-Report-VP22_FINAL1.pdf

⁶³ https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/01/Technical-Advisory-Board-Report_P23.pdf

⁶⁴ https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/06/TAB-Report-P24_FINAL1.pdf

⁶⁵ <https://www.rd-alliance.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/12/TAB-Report-P25.pdf>

⁶⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/plenaries/p26/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

For more information about the HE funded-projects, please refer to the upcoming D3.6⁶⁷ report.

- **Official documentations**
 - *Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA)*: defines the framework and implementation strategies for future research, development and innovation in relation to the EOSC.
 - *Multi-Annual Roadmap (MAR)*: defined the planning and priority-setting component of the SRIA for the EOSC.
- **EOSC Federation**: is the technical and organizational framework that connects the EOSC system of research data and services across distributed resources in the EU and associated countries.
- **EOSC-Association (EOSC-A)**
 - *EOSC-A*: is a legal entity to govern EOSC⁶⁸ and works to implement EOSC and EOSC Federation to advance OS in the interest of creating new knowledge,
 - *EOSC-A Task Forces (TFs)*: are expert-driven working groups created to address specific challenges, priorities, or gaps in the EOSC ecosystem.
 - *EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs)*: are also an expert-driven group created to explore new opportunities and emerging areas for EOSC development. They constitute an important mechanism for collaboration on technical and related matters within the HE Co-programmed Partnership for EOSC.

Summary of domain-agnostic efforts within the EOSC ecosystem:

- The INFRAEOSC calls concretely support EOSC development and over half are domain-specific projects. However, ERA calls which indirectly support EOSC development through funded OS-related projects, are largely domain-agnostic.
- The INFRAEOSC calls also provide helpful information on satellite initiatives gravitating towards the EOSC ecosystem such as ESFRI.
- The consultation on the new SRIA emphasises challenges related to domain-agnostic approaches, particularly the combination of AI and FAIR principles.
- While the EOSC-A OAE thematic remains unchanged over the three years, the EOSC-A TFs dramatically changed providing a good source of information for future landscape analysis.
- The EOSC ecosystem comprises a broad and diverse set of domain-agnostic OS initiatives. It is important to monitor its thematic orientations as well as the policy recommendation provided by its initiatives, especially the EOSC-A TFs or the SRIA document.

⁶⁷ O'Connor, R., Grau, N., Lehtsalu, L., Claire, C., Hanahoe, H., Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D3.6: Landscape analysis on the value of RDA Outputs to EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

⁶⁸ [https://eosc.eu/eosc-association/#:~:text=The%20EOSC%20Association%20is%20the,Open%20Science%20Cloud%20\(EOSC\).](https://eosc.eu/eosc-association/#:~:text=The%20EOSC%20Association%20is%20the,Open%20Science%20Cloud%20(EOSC).)

3.1.2.1. *EOSC Horizon Europe-funded domain-agnostic projects*

Table 4 lists the INFRAEOSC projects, their name, acronym and website URL along with their respective call topics.

Table 4. INFRAEOSC funded-projects by year of the call and name of the topics of the call for proposals.

Year of the call	2021	2022	2023	2024
Number of INFRAEOSC funded-projects	10	5	7	10
Name of topics of the INFRAEOSC calls	Project acronym, title and link			
HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-01: Supporting an EOSC-ready digitally skilled workforce	Skills4EOSC - Skills for the European Open Science Commons: Creating a Training Ecosystem for Open and FAIR Science https://www.skills4eosc.eu/			
HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-02: Supporting the development and coordination of activities of the EOSC Partnership	EOSC Focus https://eosc.eu/eosc-focus-project/			
HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-03: Deploying EOSC-Core components for FAIR	FAIRCORE4EOSC - Building new EOSC-Core components to support FAIR research in science https://faircore4eosc.eu/			
HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-04: Innovative and customizable services for EOSC	AI4EOSC - Artificial Intelligence for the European Open Science Cloud https://ai4eosc.eu/			
	EuroScienceGateway - leveraging the European compute infrastructures for data-intensive research guided by FAIR principles https://galaxyproject.org/projects/esg/			
	FAIR-EASE - FAIR EArth Sciences & Environment services https://fairease.eu/			
	RAISE - Research Analysis Identifier SystEm https://raise-science.eu/			
	SciLake - Democratising and making sense out of heterogeneous scholarly content https://scilake.eu/			
HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-05: Enabling discovery and interoperability of federated research objects across scientific communities	FAIR-IMPACT - Expanding FAIR Solutions across EOSC https://fair-impact.eu/			

HORIZON-INFRA-2021-EOSC-01-06: FAIR and open data sharing in support of cancer research	EOSC4Cancer - A European-wide foundation to accelerate Data-driven Cancer Research https://eosc4cancer.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-01: Services and tools to underpin a research assessment system that incentivises open science practice	GraspOS - GraspOS: next Generation Research Assessment to Promote Open Science https://graspos.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-03: FAIR and open data sharing in support of healthy oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters	Blue-Cloud 2026 - A federated European FAIR and Open Research Ecosystem for oceans, seas, coastal and inland waters https://blue-cloud.org/
	AquaINFRA - Infrastructure for Marine and Inland Water Research https://aquainfra.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2022-EOSC-01-04: Support for initiatives helping to generate global standards, specifications and recommendations for open sharing of FAIR research data, publications and software	RDA TIGER - Research Data Alliance facilitation of Targeted International working Groups for EOSC-related Research solutions https://www.rd-alliance.org/working-groups/rda-tiger/
HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-01: Build on the science cluster approach to ensure the uptake of EOSC by research infrastructures and research communities	OSCARs - O.S.C.A.R.S. - Open Science Clusters' Action for Research and Society https://oscar-project.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-02: Development of community-based approaches for ensuring and improving the quality of scientific software and code	EVERSE - European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence https://everse.software/
HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-03: Planning, tracking, and assessing scientific knowledge production	OSTrails - Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways https://ostrails.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-04: Next generation services for operational and sustainable EOSC Core Infrastructure	EOSC Beyond - EOSC Beyond: advancing innovation and collaboration for research https://www.eosc-beyond.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2023-EOSC-01-06:	TITAN - TITAN: Trusted environments for confidential computing and secure data sharing

Trusted environments for sensitive data management in EOSC	https://titan-eosc.eu/
	EOSC ENTRUST - EOSC-ENTRUST: A European Network of TRUSTed research environments https://eosc-entrust.eu/
	SIESTA - Secure Interactive Environments for SensiTive data Analytics https://eosc-siesta.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-01: FAIR and open data sharing in support of the mission adaptation to climate change	CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC - Fair Data and Innovative Services for Magnifying the Climate Adaptation potential of European Communities https://climate-adapt4eosc.eu/
	FAIR2Adapt - FAIR to Adapt to Climate Change https://fair2adapt-eosc.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-02: Supporting the EOSC Partnership in further consolidating the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem	EOSC Gravity - Supporting the EOSC Partnership in further consolidating the coordination and sustainability of the EOSC ecosystem https://eosc.eu/eosc-gravity/
HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-03: Enabling a network of EOSC federated and trustworthy repositories and enhancing the framework of generic and discipline specific services for data and other research digital objects	FIDELIS - FIDELIS: Establishing A European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories https://eden-fidelis.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-04: Long-term access and preservation infrastructure development for EOSC, including data quality aspect	EOSC EDEN - Enhancing Digital preservation strategies at European and National level https://eden-fidelis.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-01-05: Innovative and customizable services for EOSC Exchange	LUMEN - Linked User-driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network https://lumenproject.eu/
	EOSC Data Commons - Services for inter- and cross-disciplinary data discovery, access, sharing and reuse in the EOSC Federation https://www.eosc-data-commons.eu/
	DataGEMS - Data Discovery Platform with Generalized Exploratory, Management, and Search Capabilities https://datagems.eu/

	RAISE suite - FAIR data from collection to exploitation https://raise-suite.eu/
HORIZON-INFRA-2024-EOSC-02-01: Future Engagement Model for the EOSC Federation	EOSC United - Coordination and Support Action for the Future engagement model for the EOSC Federation https://eosc.eu/eosc-united/

At the time of writing, there are 24 ongoing INFRAEOSC projects that can be found on the EOSC projects webpage⁶⁹. Based on their names, 14 of 24 current INFRAEOSC can be considered as domain-agnostic (Table 4 and HE projects dataset available attached to the report as title: D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_HorizonEurope_projects)⁷⁰. For practical reasons, the project's URL is not attached to the project's name but can be retrieved from Table 4.

Some INFRAEOSC projects focus their activities on EOSC federation or coordination, such as EOSC Gravity, EOSC United, EOSC Beyond and RDA TIGER; while others address the implementation of FAIR principles across the research output lifecycle. These include projects focusing on research identifiers (RAISE), trusted and secured repositories (TITAN, EOSC ENTRUST, SIESTA and FIDELIS), interoperable services and research outputs (EOSC Data Commons), computational and software aspects (EVERSE), data preservation (EOSC EDEN), and data discovery (DataGEMS and SciLake). Other projects focus on research innovation (EOSC Beyond) and assessment of OS and FAIR practices (OSTrails and RAISE suite). For further details on INFRAEOSC projects and their alignment with RDA WGs activity, we recommend reading the upcoming D3.6⁷¹ report.

Since the publication of the previous report MS10⁷² in June 2025, there were no new INFRAEOSC projects. However, eight projects have ended: HORIZON-ZEN, FAIR-IMPACT, FAIRCORE4EOSC, EOSC4CANCER, EOSC Focus; EuroScienceGate, AI4EOSC and FAIR-EASE and Skills4EOSC; and four will conclude at the end of this year: SciLake, GraspOS, CRAFT-OA and RDA TIGER. The new pool of INFRAEOSC projects will be renewed in 2026, with 13 new projects expected to be funded through the 2025 Research Infrastructures (RIs) work programme⁷³ which includes the INFRAEOSC call for proposals.

The analysis of the EOSC- and OS-related HE-funded projects conducted in the upcoming D3.6⁷⁴ show the involvement of projects funded under the Widening Participation and Strengthening the European Research Area (WIDERA) work programme⁷⁵ into the EOSC development. These projects funded under the Reforming and Enhancing the European Research (ERA) call of WIDERA work programme focus on OS⁷⁶ priority area of the European Research Area Policy call “Enabling open science via sharing and re-use of data, including through the EOSC.”⁷⁷

⁶⁹ eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/#openproject (accessed 2025.11.13)

⁷⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034188>

⁷¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

⁷² doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733

⁷³ research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/funding/funding-opportunities/funding-programmes-and-open-calls/horizon-europe/research-infrastructures_en (accessed 2025.11.13)

⁷⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

⁷⁵ ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/wp-call/2021-2022/wp-11-widening-participation-and-strengthening-the-european-research-area_horizon-2021-2022_en.pdf (accessed 2025.11.14)

⁷⁶ www.ncpwideranet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/ERA_Factsheet_No_5_03.pdf (accessed 2025.12.19)

⁷⁷ european-research-area.ec.europa.eu/era-structural-policies-2025-2027 (accessed 2025.12.19)

Table 5. WIDERA funded-projects falling under the OS area, by year of the call and name of the topics of the call for proposals.

Year of the call	2021	2022	2023	2024
Number of ERA-OS projects ⁷⁸	7	6	1	3
Name of topics of the ERA-OS call	Project acronym, title and link			
HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-40: Modelling and quantifying the impacts of open science practice	PathOS - Open Science Impact Pathways https://pathos-project.eu/			
HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-41: Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice	WorldFAIR - Global cooperation on FAIR data policy and practice https://worldfair-project.eu/			
HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-43: Capacity-building for institutional open access publishing across Europe	DIAMAS - Developing Institutional open Access publishing Models to Advance Scholarly communication https://diamasproject.eu/			
HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-44: Societal trust in science, research and innovation	POIESIS - Probing the impact of integrity and integration on societal trust in science https://poiesis-project.eu/			
	IANUS - INspiring and ANchoring TrUst in Science https://trustinscience.eu/			
	VERITY - deVELOping scientific Research with ethIcs and inTEgrity for shARed benefitS https://www.verityproject.eu/			
HORIZON-WIDERA-2021-ERA-01-45: Support to changes in the assessment of research and researchers to reward the practice of open science.	OPUS - Open Universal Science http://opusproject.eu			
HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-40: Stepping-up institutional and territorial changes towards open and responsible research and innovation	REINFORCING - Responsible tErritories and Institutions eNable and Foster Open Research and inClusive Innovation for traNsitions Governance https://reinforcing.eu/about			

⁷⁸ https://www.ncpwideranet.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/ERA_Factsheet_No_5_03.pdf (accessed 2025.11.10)

HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-41: Increasing the reproducibility of scientific results	OSIRIS - Open Science to Increase Reproducibility in Science https://osiris4r.eu/
	TIER2 - Enhancing trust, integrity and efficiency in research through next-level reproducibility impact pathways https://tier2-project.eu/
	iRISE - improving Reproducibility In SciencE https://irise-project.eu/
HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-42: Supporting the development of aligned policies for open access books and monographs	PALOMERA - Policy Alignment of Open access Monographs in the European Research Area https://operas-eu.org/projects/palomera/
HORIZON-WIDERA-2022-ERA-01-44: Developing and piloting training on the practice of open and responsible research and innovation	PATTERN - Piloting open and responsible Activities and Trainings Towards the Enhancement of Researchers Networks https://www.pattern-openresearch.eu/
HORIZON-WIDERA-2023-ERA-01-07: Support to reforms of research assessment in the European Research Area	CoARA Boost - Strengthening CoARA and Enabling Systemic Reform of Research Assessment - A Booster https://coara.eu/coara-boost-project/
HORIZON-WIDERA-2024-ERA-01-07: Capacity building on Intellectual Property (IP) management to support open science	IP4OS - IP4OS Unpacking the possibilities of Intellectual Properties for Open Science https://www.ip4os.eu/
HORIZON-WIDERA-2024-ERA-01-08: Global cooperation in not-for-profit open access publishing	ALMASI - Aligning and Mutualizing Nonprofit Open Access Publishing Services Internationally https://almasiproject.org/fr/bienvenue/
HORIZON-WIDERA-2024-ERA-01-09: Support to the development and implementation of policies and practices for reproducibility of scientific results	TRUSTparency - Increasing reproducibility through the co-creation of interventions that support a transparent and trustworthy research ecosystem https://trustparency-project.eu/

Table 5 presents the OS-related ERA projects, here referred as ERA-OS, their name, acronym and website URL along with their respective call topics. The associated data also is attached to this report⁷⁹.

All seventeen projects are domain-agnostic either aim to strengthen ERA policy (CoARA Boost) or promote general OS practices (OPUS, PathOS and WorldFAIR). Several projects focus on assessing OS and FAIR practices (TRUSTparency, OSIRIS, TIER2, iRISE) and their impact on research reliability (REINFORCING, POIESIS, IANUS, VERITY and PATTERN). Finally, a subset of projects specifically addresses OS publications access issues (IPOS, ALMASI, PALOMERA, and DIAMAS). For practical reasons, the project's URL is not attached to the project's name but can be retrieved from Table 5. For further details on ERA-OS projects and their alignment with RDA WGs activity, we recommend reading the upcoming D3.6⁸⁰ report.

There are numerous initiatives related to INFRAEOSC calls which are important to track and are mentioned in the Research Infrastructures (RIs) call for proposals. Here are some examples of those domain-agnostic initiatives:

- European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI)⁸¹, which aims to provide a coherent and strategy-led approach to policy making and investment in RI. It has WGs and TFs⁸² whose purpose is to periodically update ESFRI's RIs and publish these updates in the Roadmap, with a new edition planned for 2026. There is only one non-domain specific area in ESFRI which is Data, Computing, and Digital Research Infrastructures⁸³;
- European Research Infrastructure Consortia (ERIC)⁸⁴, which establishes a legal form that facilitates the establishment and operation of RI with European interest;
- European Data Spaces⁸⁵ with fourteen domain-specific data spaces and domain-agnostic fields such as skills, mobility and manufacturing;
- EGI⁸⁶ aims to support data-intensive research with a wide range of advanced computing services;
- GEANT⁸⁷ which is a collaboration of European National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) to develop, deliver and promote advanced networks and associated e-infrastructure services;

⁷⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034188>

⁸⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

⁸¹ www.esfri.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁸² www.esfri.eu/working-groups (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁸³ landscape2024.esfri.eu/landscape-analysis/thematic-areas/data-computing-and-digital-research-infrastructures/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁸⁴ research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/european-research-infrastructures/eric_en (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁸⁵ digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁸⁶ www.egi.eu/about/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁸⁷ geant.org/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

- Group of Senior Officials on global Research Infrastructures⁸⁸ aims to help RIs to be ‘global’ thought a set of fourteen key principles/criteria⁸⁹,
- OpenAIRE⁹⁰ which is a trusted infrastructure for open access, data sharing and scholarly communication.

It is also recommended to track certifications bodies such as CoreTrustSeal⁹¹ or NestorSeal⁹² to stay updated on the latest recommendations.

The upcoming D3.6⁹³ report map the scope of RDA TIGER supported RDA WGs with ESFRI and ERICs infrastructures, providing a valuable first insight on the shared interests and domains of activity of the two communities.

3.1.2.2. *EOSC Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda and Multi Annual Roadmap*

Since the publication of the first D3.1⁹⁴ report in June 2023, two versions of the SRIA have been published⁹⁵: v1.2⁹⁶ in 2023 and v1.3⁹⁷ in 2024, and reflect the incorporation of the different Multi Annual Roadmaps (MAR).

The seven areas relating to the technical challenges remain unchanged:

- Identifiers,
- Metadata, and ontologies;
- FAIR metrics and certification;
- Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure;
- User environments;
- Resource provider environments,
- EOSC Interoperability Framework

As well as the seven boundary conditions:

- Rules of Participation;
- Landscape monitoring;

⁸⁸ www.gsogri.org/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁸⁹ www.gsogri.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/11/gso_framework_criteria.pdf (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁹⁰ www.openaire.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁹¹ www.coretrustseal.org/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁹² www.langzeitarchivierung.de/Webs/nestor/EN/Services/nestor_Siegel/nestor_siegel_node.html (accessed 2025.11.19)

⁹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

⁹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

⁹⁵ <https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/sria-mar/> (accessed 2025.11.13)

⁹⁶ Horizon Europe Co-programmed Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). (2023). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (v1.2, 2023) (1.2). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17582638>

⁹⁷ Horizon Europe Co-programmed Partnership for the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). (2024). Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) (v1.3, 2024) (1.3). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17582648>

- Business models;
- Skills and training;
- Rewards and recognition;
- Communication,
- Widening to public and private sectors and going global

The SRIA v2.0 is still under consultation and is expected to be completed before 2026⁹⁸. The discussions focus on the chapters already defined in the new version of the SRIA, as well as the challenges addressed under the following chapters:

- Interoperability;
- FAIR Data and Metadata;
- AI for FAIR and FAIR for AI;
- Services;
- Governance.

All chapters address domain-agnostic topics, with a focus on service and integration within EOSC Nodes or Data Space. The place of AI is still under discussion; either to be a dedicated chapter or integrate into other chapters. Meanwhile, training and skills topics are covered in the sustainability sub-chapter of the FAIR Data and Metadata chapter.

The RDA TIGER upcoming D3.6⁹⁹ report provides a deep understanding of the SRIA implementation challenges and MAR and their alignment with RDA WGs.

3.1.2.3. EOSC Federation

The revised version of EOSC Federation Handbook is scheduled for release in December 2025¹⁰⁰. In parallel, the EOSC Federation Build-up groups and sub groups¹⁰¹ focused on: Capabilities, Resources, Governance, Cybersecurity, have published recommendations to assemble the essential building blocks for enrolling and federating the Nodes, as well as the onboarding of external resources. These outputs include the EOSC Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure Architecture 2025¹⁰², and the Technical Interoperability in the EOSC Federation and initial gap analysis¹⁰³, (both provided by the EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF), and the Registration of EOSC Research Product

⁹⁸ eosc.eu/eosc-about/sria-mar/sria-2-0-community-consultation/ (accessed 2025.11.11)

⁹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

¹⁰⁰ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-federation-handbook/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

¹⁰¹ eosc.eu/news/eosc-federation-builds-momentum-prior-to-symposium-launch/ (accessed 2025.11.11)

¹⁰² Kanellopoulos, C., Adomeit, M., Ardizzzone, V., Florio, L., Giacomini, F., Groep, D., Hardt, M., Kálmán, T., Kuczyński, T., Liampotis, N., Short, H., Sidorova, I., Michal, Š., & Wierenga, K. (2025). EOSC AAI Architecture 2025 (March 2025). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15388270>

¹⁰³ Scardaci, D. O., Dimper, R., Wilk, R., Gonzalez Guardia, E., Portier, M., & Van de Sanden, M. (2025). Technical interoperability in the EOSC Federation and initial gap analysis. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17507570>

Catalogues in the EOSC EU Nodes¹⁰⁴. All these federation efforts are available in the Zenodo repository of the EOSC Association (ESOC-A)¹⁰⁵.

In addition, two open calls have been launched to support the growth of the EOSC Federation^{106, 107}:

- The Preparatory Grant, which aims work of potential future EOSC nodes (national, multi-country or thematic);
- The Inter Project Grant, which aims to expand the services offered through the EOSC Federation, and demonstrating a clear benefit for end users through either:
 - The development of scientific use cases that demonstrate the usefulness of the EOSC Federation, or;
 - The piloting of how new services can be added (“onboarded”) into one or more EOSC Nodes to be used by end users.

At the time of writing, most of currently enrolled initiatives in EOSC Nodes are domain-specific¹⁰⁸, and only EUDAT, for Data, Computing and Digital can be considered as domain-agnostic.

The EOSC Federation also has specific INFRAEOSC projects to support its development and expansion:

- EOSC Focus (2022-2025): has laid the groundwork for identifying potential partners and has developed methodology to facilitate the integration of research outputs into EOSC. It has recently published two reports¹⁰⁹ related to engagement and collaboration activities: the D2.2 “Engagement Activities Review”¹¹⁰, and the D3.3 “Technical Collaboration Report with other European Partnerships and Relevant Initiatives”¹¹¹. These reports provide a useful source of OS initiatives gravitating around the EOSC ecosystem.
- EOSC Gravity¹¹² continue the EOSC Focus activities on expanding the EOSC community through outreach and engagement activities,
- EOSC United project¹¹³ supports uniting the research community within the EOSC Federation.

¹⁰⁴ Manghi, P., Athanasiou, S., Karmas, T., & Szegedi, P. (2025). Registration of EOSC Research Product Catalogues in the EOSC EU Node (3.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15516020>

¹⁰⁵ zenodo.org/communities/eosc/records?q=&l=list&p=1&s=10&sort=newest (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁰⁶ eosc.eu/news/open-calls-to-grow-the-eosc-federation/ (accessed 2025.11.11)

¹⁰⁷ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/contributing-to-the-build-up-phase/ (accessed 2025.11.11)

¹⁰⁸ eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/EOSC-A_GA11_20251010_Slide-deck.pdf (accessed 2025.11.11)

¹⁰⁹ Caetano, I., Galica, N., Hasani-Mavriqi, I., Märkälä, A., de Jong, F., Reichmann, S., Sanchez-Santana, B., Schröder-Pander, F., & Vins, D. (2025). EOSC Focus - Deliverable 2.2 - Engagement Activities Review. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17572839>

¹¹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17572839>

¹¹¹ De Loof, C., de Mello Castro Giroletti, J., Robertson, D., Schröder-Pander, F., & Caetano, I. (2025). EOSC Focus - D3.3 - Technical collaboration report with other European Partnerships and relevant initiatives. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17574006>

¹¹² eosc.eu/eosc-gravity/ (accessed 2025.12.12)

¹¹³ eosc.eu/eosc-united/ (accessed 2025.12.12)

3.1.2.4. EOSC Association, Task Forces and Opportunity Area Expert Groups

The EOSC association (EOSC-A) Task Forces (TFs) aims to liaise with the INFRAEOSC projects, as above, and also with the seven current EOSC Opportunity Area Expert Groups (OAEs) which are¹¹⁴:

- Persistent Identifiers, Metadata;
- Ontologies and Interoperability;
- FAIR Assessment and Alignment;
- User and Resource Environments, Skills;
- Training, Rewards, Recognition and Upscaling;
- Open Scholarly Communication;
- Research Software, which was added in 2025.

The strategic organisation of the EOSC-A TF is structured around a three-year period, with each of the TF having its own charter and planned output phase. During the 2021-2023 period¹¹⁵ thirteen EOSC-A TFs were active, grouped under the following four domain-agnostic headings: Metadata; Research Careers; Technical Challenges; and Sustaining EOSC.

In contrast, for the 2024-2026 period, both the number and focus of EOSC-A TFs have dramatically changed, with only four TFs¹¹⁶ which are currently supported:

- EOSC Technical and Semantic Interoperability TF¹¹⁷, which has published two recommendations in 2025:
 - EOSC AAI Architecture 2025¹¹⁸ (Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure);
 - Technical interoperability in the EOSC Federation and initial gap analysis¹¹⁹
- FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects TF¹²⁰,
- EOSC-A Long-Term Data Retention TF¹²¹;
- Health Data TF¹²²; which is the only domain-specific TF with a focus introduced for the health discipline.

The EOSC-A TF recommendations can be found on each TF's webpage or in the Macro-Roadmap¹²³, the interactive catalogue tracking the results of EOSC projects and EOSC-A TFs. EOSC-A TFs, and OAEs also offer another tracker of domain-agnostic activity across the EOSC ecosystem.

¹¹⁴ eosc.eu/eosc-opportunity-area-expert-groups/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹¹⁵ eosc.eu/eosc-association/eosc-task-forces/eosc-a-task-forces-2021-2023/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹¹⁶ eosc.eu/eosc-association/eosc-task-forces/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹¹⁷ eosc.eu/advisory-groups/technical-and-semantic-interoperability-task-force/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹¹⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15388270>

¹¹⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17507570>

¹²⁰ eosc.eu/advisory-groups/fair-metrics-and-digital-objects-task-force/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹²¹ eosc.eu/advisory-groups/long-term-data-retention-task-force/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹²² eosc.eu/advisory-groups/health-data-task-force/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹²³ eosc.eu/eosc-about/eosc-macro-roadmap/?_type_of_result_mrm=report (accessed 2025.11.25)

Moreover, the forthcoming RDA TIGER D3.6¹²⁴ report maps EOSC-A TFs and OAEs with RDA WGs activities, providing valuable insights into how these areas are being tackled within the RDA community.

3.1.3. Within global domain-agnostic initiatives

In this section, we explore the domain-agnostic activities among the global initiatives and report its updates and trends.

The four main global initiatives explored are:

- **CODATA**: plays an internationally recognised role to advance OS and the FAIR principles and has brought significant expertise to major policy and strategy documents (e.g. Turning FAIR into Reality, and the UNESCO Recommendation on OS). Among the ways CODATA aims to achieve these priorities are through Task Groups (TGs) and Working Groups (WGs).
 - *CODATA Task Groups (TGs)*: are groups of scientists, researchers and data experts who work together on a specific problem or theme to advance the state of data management.
 - *CODATA Working Groups (WGs)*: differ from TGs in that they are set up by the CODATA Executive Committee and are expected to complete their activity within a set period of not normally more than two years.
- **ReSA**: aims to “bring research software communities together to collaborate on the advancement of the research software ecosystem, to achieve the vision that research software and those who develop and maintain it are recognised and valued as fundamental and vital to research worldwide.”¹²⁵
 - *ReSA Task Forces (TFs)*: aims to achieve ReSA goals, and focus on particular domain-agnostic concerns that are of relevance to research software engineers
- **Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC)**: aims to encourage cooperation, alignment and ultimately interoperability among a number of OS clouds or common initiatives.
 - *GOSC Working Groups (WGs)*: are expert groups focusing on key thematic areas relevant to connecting and aligning GOSC from different regions and initiatives around the world.
- **United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)**: is a “specialised agency of the United Nations with the aim of promoting world peace and security through international cooperation”¹²⁶ and has published a set of principles and practices to guide what OS is and how to make scientific research accessible to everyone¹²⁷

¹²⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

¹²⁵ www.researchsoft.org/taskforces/

¹²⁶ [ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization \(UNESCO\)#:~:text=United%20Nations%20Educational%2C%20Scientific%20and%20Cultural%20Organization%20\(UNESCO\).-Glossary%3AUnited%20Nations](http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:United_Nations_Educational_Scientific_and_Cultural_Organization_(UNESCO)#:~:text=United%20Nations%20Educational%2C%20Scientific%20and%20Cultural%20Organization%20(UNESCO).-Glossary%3AUnited%20Nations)

¹²⁷ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about> (accessed 2025.11.14)

- *UNESCO Working Groups (WGs)*: are expert groups supporting the implementation of the UNESCO Recommendation on OS over specific thematic groups

Summary of domain-agnostic efforts among the global initiatives:

- CODATA and ReSA constitute an important reservoir of resources which, thanks to the regular renewal of their groups, provide a pool of up-to-date and relevant topics.
- GOS and UNESCO offer a long-term vision of OS ambitions and realise this vision through widely recognised recommendations.
- All these organisations maintain numerous partnerships with other institutions and stakeholders, making them a rich source of entities addressing challenges related to OS.
- RSE 2025 conference (RSECon25) places a strong emphasis on a human-centric approach, thus highlighting the importance of an informed community. Conferences appear to be a crucial venue for exchanging ideas, discussing trending topics and exploring how to address them.

3.1.3.1. CODATA domain-agnostic groups

Recently, the renewal of the Task Groups (TGs) for the 2025-2027 period shows that 6 out of 8 are related to domain-agnostic¹²⁸ fields:

- Big Data Curation and Curation Sustainability (new TG), which focuses on challenges and best practices in the curation of Big data;
- Open Science Cloud Service XI Metadata TG (new TG), which aims to build a metadata schema and empower engineering technical resilience with strong connection with OS e-infrastructures;
- Open Tools and Visitation Frameworks for Global Research Assessment Reform (new TG); which aims to co-create open, interoperable and ethical frameworks that connect research assessment reform with data visitation technologies and empowering equitable participation across the Global South;
- Research Data Quality Management Across the Data Lifecycle (new TG), which aims to provide best practices guidance and define potential lack of data quality rules;
- Citizen Science for the SDGs (continuing TG), which aims continuing to provide guidance to work between data and policy frameworks and make progress towards interdisciplinary standards for citizen data and metadata;
- DRUM – Digital Representation of Units of Measure (continuing TG), which aims to continue to make recommendations for representations for ‘counting’ and create ‘simple and easy to use’ solutions.

alongside the long-running Fundamental Physical Constants TG¹²⁹.

¹²⁸ codata.org/events/general-assembly/general-assembly-2025/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹²⁹ codata.org/initiatives/task-groups/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

Several CODATA WGs are active under CODATA's 2023-2027 Strategic Plan¹³⁰, such as

- Research Data Management Terminology (RDMT) WG¹³¹, which aims to gather the key terms needed for a common understanding of the research data management domain and has recently released its new machine-actionable version in Sept 2025;
- WGs associated with Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC)¹³²; which aims to address alignment and interoperability issues of cloud infrastructure and encourage their cooperation, details are provided below in the section 3.1.5;
- OneGeochemistry WG¹³³, established as a result of the EU-funded WorldFAIR project¹³⁴, aims to create a global geochemical data network that facilitates and promotes discovery of, and access to geochemical data by providing standards and best practices guidelines;
- Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CFID) development WG¹³⁵, also established as a result of the WorldFAIR project, aims to develop and support a new set of implementation profiles on existing standard and technology, as well as renewing the existing profiles based on feedback, to support interoperability in both human- and machine-actionable ways.

CODATA's TGs have been recently renewed and are primarily focused on domain-agnostic approaches.

3.1.3.2. *Research Software Alliance Task Forces*

There is currently three ongoing ReSA TFs¹³⁶:

- Actionable Guidelines for FAIR Research Software¹³⁷;
- Policies in Research Organisations for Research Software¹³⁸;
- Research Software Authorship and Contribution¹³⁹;
- Succession Planning for Research Software¹⁴⁰

One TF is still under review at this time of writing namely, FAIR Principles for Research Software.

Finally, the Research Software Engineering Conference 2025 (RESCon25)¹⁴¹ held in September 2025, focused on two core themes: the Research Software Engineering (RSE) and Research excellence,

¹³⁰codata.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/10/CODATA-Strategic-Plan_-_Data-to-Improve-our-World-2023-FINAL-E-ndorsed-by-General-Assembly.pdf (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹³¹codata.org/initiatives/data-science-and-stewardship/rdm-terminology-wg/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹³²codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work/global-open-science-cloud/working-groups/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹³³codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work/worldfair-2/onegeochemistry-wg/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹³⁴worldfair-project.eu/

¹³⁵codata.org/apply-to-join-the-cross-domain-interoperability-framework-cdif-working-group-or-advisory-group-deadline-30-september/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹³⁶www.researchsoft.org/taskforces/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹³⁷www.researchsoft.org/tf-actionable-fair4rs/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹³⁸www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-resa-policies-research-organisations-research-software-pro4rs/posts/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹³⁹www.researchsoft.org/tf-authorship-contribution/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁴⁰www.researchsoft.org/tf-succession-planning/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁴¹secon25.society-rse.org/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

which address the foundations of modern research, and the RSE as Digital Research Infrastructure, with a strong focus on human-centric approach. Satellite events also supported this human-centric perspective, by including the Training Community Day and the RSE leaders and aspiring leaders meetings¹⁴². Resources of the RESCon25 are available in the event Zenodo repository¹⁴³.

3.1.3.3. *Global Open Science Cloud domain-agnostic working groups*

Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC) Working groups (WGs) remain unchanged and address a set of domain-agnostic issues, such as Strategy, Governance and Sustainability; Policy and Legal; Technical Infrastructure; and Data Interoperability¹⁴⁴, while its case studies tackle primarily domain-specific issues (see section.3.2.3.2).

3.1.3.4. *UNESCO domain-agnostic working groups*

The UNESCO Recommendation on OS¹⁴⁵ was adopted in 2021 and to support its implementation UNESCO has launched five ad-hoc Working Groups (WGs) focusing on high-impact areas for OS¹⁴⁶ which are:

- OS Capability Building, aims to collect existing training modules on OS for different OS stakeholders in order to identify gaps;
- OS Policies and Policy Instruments; aims to assist UNESCO Secretariat in developing a global repository of OS policy and instruments;
- OS Funding and Incentives, aims to collect proposal for regional and thematic OS funding and provide recommendations on research careers assessment and evaluation criteria;
- OS Infrastructures, aims to map, analyse gaps and produce best practices for OS platforms to improve sharing of knowledge;
- OS Monitoring Framework, aims to provide a global OS monitoring through a set of principles.

The OS Infrastructures WG¹⁴⁷ is the only WG focusing on domain-specific area and has shown a recent activity.

All digital resources collected to promote learning about OS and to support teaching in line with the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on OS are accessible in the UNESCO catalogue¹⁴⁸. These include domain-agnostic resources, such as the Re-using and repurposing other people's data¹⁴⁹ or the Repository Toolkit¹⁵⁰. In addition to offering a rich ecosystem of OS resources, the UNESCO catalogue

¹⁴² rsecon25.society-rse.org/satellite-events/ (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁴³ zenodo.org/communities/rsecon25/records?q=&l=list&p=2&s=10&sort=newest (accessed 2025.12.21)

¹⁴⁴ goscloud.net/workingGroups (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁴⁵ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁴⁶ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/implementation (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁴⁷ unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000393106 (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁴⁸ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/capacity-building-index (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁴⁹ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/re-using-and-repurposing-other-peoples-data?hub=686 (accessed 2025.11.14)

¹⁵⁰ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/repository-toolkit?hub=686 (accessed 2025.11.14)

also brings together numerous organisations, academies, coalitions or funders¹⁵¹ engaged in OS initiatives.

3.2. Developments in domain-specific initiatives

3.2.1. Within RDA community

In this section, we explore the domain-specific activities among the RDA community and report its updates and trends.

Two main activities of RDA are explored:

- **RDA groups**^{152,153}
 - *Interest Groups (IGs)*: serve as a platform of exchange among individuals wishing to explore a shared interest. Endorsed IG remains active as long as they continue to contribute to their objectives. IG produces outputs such as surveys, recommendations, reports and can initiate new WG.
 - *Working Groups (WGs)*: have a specific function in producing concrete outputs or recommendations on a specific topic. They have a fixed period of time (12-18months) to complete their task. The WG outputs can include technical specification, standards or best practices as well as conceptual model or framework or implemented policies.
 - *WGs supported by RDA TIGER*: these are RDA WGs that have benefited from RDA TIGER services such as facilitation, landscape awareness or communication.
- **RDA Outputs**¹⁵⁴: RDA Outputs and Recommendations have changed in between D3.1 and D3.4, with clearer definitions of an RDA Recommendation and an Output, and how these differ
 - *RDA Recommendations*: are produced by RDA WGs and are the official, endorsed results of the RDA and considered our ‘flagship’ Outputs;
 - *Supporting Outputs*: are useful solutions from RDA WGs, IGs, or CoPs, but may not be as clearly adoptable as RDA Recommendations;
 - *Other Outputs*: are used to describe resources that have been published on the RDA website following a request by a WG, IG or CoP, but have received no level of endorsement. They could include workshop reports, published articles, survey results, etc.

Summary of domain-specific efforts within the RDA community:

¹⁵¹ www.unesco.org/en/global-open-science-partnership?hub=686

¹⁵² www.rd-alliance.org/about-rda-groups/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁵³ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁵⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/ (accessed 2025.12.20)

- The overall distribution between domain-agnostic and domain-specific WGs appears balanced, compared to RDA IGs. This difference can be explained by the more exploratory nature of IGs which offers a broader topics platform of discussion.
- Among all the RDA WGs and IGs, the RDA TIGER supported groups appear to be the most prolific, with five Recommend and Outputs released over the past six months.

3.2.1.1. RDA domain-specific groups

Table 6 shows the current number of domain-specific RDA WGs and IGs, at the time of writing.

Table 6. Numbers of domain-specific RDA WGs and IGs

	Number of RDA WGs	Number of RDA IGs
Domain specific	23 ¹⁵⁵	18 ¹⁵⁶
Total	45 ¹⁵⁷	51 ¹⁵⁸

Since the publication of the MS10¹⁵⁹ report in June 2025, the number of domain-specific RDA WGs has remained unchanged, while one RDA IGs has been removed from the list of domain-specific RDA IGs¹⁶⁰. Moreover, the creation of two RDA WGs: the FAIR Run Time Environments WG in October 2025, and the Salmon Ontology Development WG in July 2025, indicate that changes in the categorisation of RDA groups have taken place since June 2025.

Table 7. Domain-specific RDA WGs supported by RDA TIGER.

Date (YY-MM-DD)	Name and link
2023-10-16	EOSC-Future/RDA Artificial Intelligence & Data Visitation WG
2023-10-17	Harmonised terminologies and schemas for FAIR data in materials science and related domains WG*
2024-02-02	Wind Energy Community Standards WG*
2024-02-09	Building Immune Digital Twins WG*

¹⁵⁵www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences (accessed 2025.11.10)

¹⁵⁶www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=interest-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁵⁷www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Csocial-sciences%2Cdomain-agnostic%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences (accessed 2025.11.10)

¹⁵⁸www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=interest-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences%2Cdomain-agnostic (accessed 2025.11.10)

¹⁵⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

¹⁶⁰www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=working-group&_primary_domain=natural-sciences%2Cengineering-and-technology%2Cagricultural-and-veterinary-sciences%2Csocial-sciences&_sort=date_desc (accessed 2025.11.13)

2024-03-09	FAIRification of Genomic Annotations WG*
2024-05-09	Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data WG*
2024-05-22	Ethics in Agricultural (Ag) Data WG
2024-05-22	Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) WG*
2024-06-01	Multi-omics Metadata Standards Integration (MOMSI) WG
2024-06-26	Health Data Commons GORC Profile WG*
2025-08-26	Computational Modelling of Health Data WG*

* indicates WGs who have received RDA TIGER support from their inception.

As mentioned in 3.1.1. section, no new RDA WGs have received facilitation support from RDA TIGER since the MS10¹⁶¹ report. However, RDA TIGER has supported in total 11 out of 23 domain-specific RDA WGs, of which seven have received RDA TIGER support since their inception (Table 7).

3.2.1.2. RDA domain-specific outputs

As mentioned in section 3.1.1.2-RDA domain-agnostic outputs, 5 out of 8 of the new outputs published since MS10¹⁶² report are domain-specific.

The Wind Energy Community Standards WG, supported by RDA TIGER, is the one WG that has published a WG recommendation: “Best Practice Recommendations for Improving FAIR Data Maturity in Wind Energy”¹⁶³.

The Artificial Intelligence and Data Visitation WG¹⁶⁴, also supported by RDA TIGER, published a set of outputs¹⁶⁵ classified under two other categories:

- Supporting Outputs: the “Adding Data Visitation Language to an IRB protocol”, the ‘Adding Data Visitation language to ICFs”, “AIDV-WG Shared Citation Library” and the “System Security Assessment Plan Template”;
- Other Output: “Geographies of Trust: AI, Biomedicine, and the Next Era of Federated and Visiting Data Models”.

While these outputs do not appear in the Other Outputs category¹⁶⁶, they are tagged under the same category and can be found on the Output and Recommendations homepage¹⁶⁷.

¹⁶¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

¹⁶² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

¹⁶³ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/wind-energy-community-standards-wg/outputs/?output=198686 (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁶⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

¹⁶⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/artificial-intelligence-and-data-visitation-aidv-wg/outputs/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

¹⁶⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_output_type=working-group-supporting-output&_sort=date_desc (accessed 2025.11.19)

¹⁶⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/recommendations-and-outputs/outputs/?_sort=date_desc (accessed 2025.11.19)

3.2.2. Within EOSC ecosystem

In this section, we explore the domain-specific activities among the EOSC ecosystem and report its updates and trends.

Two main activities of EOSC ecosystem are explored, both related to the EOSC implementation

- **Horizon Europe projects:**
 - *INFRAEOSC projects:* serve the EOSC ambition of contributing to a web of FAIR research data where researchers and innovators can publish, find and reuse data, tools and services for research and innovation.
 - For more information about the EOSC and OS related HE funded-projects, please refer to the upcoming D3.6¹⁶⁸ report.
- **EOSC Federation:** is the technical and organizational framework that connects the EOSC system of research data and services across distributed resources in the EU and associated countries.

Summary of domain-specific efforts within the EOSC ecosystem:

- The domain-specific approach of the EOSC ecosystem addresses wide and global challenges such as environment, earth observation, health, and climate change, as well as issues related to sensitive data, tackled by various disciplines such as health but also energy, physics and space engineering.
- Although slightly less than half of the INFRAEOSC projects address a specific discipline, a large proportion consists of multidisciplinary projects that contribute significantly to broadening the disciplines studied.
- The EOSC ecosystem provides a rich environment for tracking domain-specific initiatives and the resources they have produced, as well as for mapping the institutions and stakeholders involved in global challenges and competitiveness.

3.2.2.1. EOSC Horizon Europe-funded domain-specific projects

As mentioned in section 3.1.2.1-EOSC Horizon Europe-funded projects, there are currently 24 ongoing INFRAEOSC projects¹⁶⁹. Ten of them can be considered domain-specific based on their name (Table 4) and address specific challenges related to oceans (Blue-Cloud 2026¹⁷⁰, AquaINFRA¹⁷¹), and climate issues (CLIMATE-ADAPT4EOSC¹⁷² and FAIR2Adapt¹⁷³). While the TITAN¹⁷⁴, EOSC-ENTRUST¹⁷⁵

¹⁶⁸ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

¹⁶⁹ eosc.eu/horizon-europe-projects/#openproject (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷⁰ blue-cloud.org/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷¹ aquainfra.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷² climate-adapt4eosc.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷³ fair2adapt-eosc.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷⁴ titan-eosc.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷⁵ eosc-entrust.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

and SIESTA¹⁷⁶ projects were considered domain-agnostic because they address data security issues, they mainly focus on health data security and therefore also be considered domain-specific.

LUMEN¹⁷⁷ and OSCARS¹⁷⁸ are the two INFRAEOSC projects addressing different domain-specific issues through a cross-disciplinary and multidisciplinary approach. The LUMEN project, for the Linked User-Driven Multidisciplinary Exploration Network, aims to foster cross-domain collaboration and discovery processes in four academic areas:

- Mathematics;
- Social Science and Humanities;
- Earth System;
- Molecular Dynamics.

Table 8. Number of the OSCARS funded projects from the two OSCARS Open Calls by domain of discipline and Science cluster

Domain	Earth and Environmental Sciences	Astronomy and Particle Physics	Life Sciences	Photon and Neutron Science	Social Sciences and Humanities	Across or outside the domains covered by the clusters
Name of the cluster	ENVRI Science ¹⁷⁹	ESCAPE ¹⁸⁰	LS RI ¹⁸¹	PaNOSC ¹⁸²	SSHOC ¹⁸³	-
Number of project funded	9	11	9	8	12	18

The OSCARS project, for ‘Open Science Clusters’ Action for Research and Society’, focuses on five thematic science clusters (Table 8). Its goal is to co-develop and cross-adopt a shared service model¹⁸⁴ that federate access to data, tools, workflow, and training across thematic services.

Through two OSCARS Open Calls, the project aims to engage a broad range of communities in the OS. The second Open Call¹⁸⁵ closed in May 2025. Although the results have not yet been officially

¹⁷⁶ eosc-siesta.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷⁷ lumenproject.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷⁸ oscars-project.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁷⁹ envri.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁸⁰ projectescape.eu/about-us (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁸¹ lifescience-ri.eu/home.html (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁸² www.panosc.eu/about-panosc/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁸³ www.sshopencloud.eu/news/sshoc-ssh-open-cluster (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁸⁴ oscars-project.eu/science-clusters-services (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁸⁵ oscars-project.eu/oscars-2nd-open-call-open-science-projects-and-services (accessed 2025.11.20)

published, 12 projects have been selected¹⁸⁶: two in the Earth and Environmental Sciences, two in Astronomy and Particle Physics, one in Life Sciences, two in Photon and Neutron Science and two in Social Sciences and Humanities (Table 6). In total, 67 projects are now supported by OSCARS. Finally, the recently published OSCARS report D3.2 Competence Centres concepts and activities (pre)existing in EOSC¹⁸⁷ offers a valuable overview and synthesis of current practices, conceptual frameworks, and policy recommendations emerging from both ongoing and past EOSC-related projects.

The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework (CDIF)¹⁸⁸, developed through the WorldFAIR project¹⁸⁹ and completed in 2024, is now being adopted in the Photon and Neutron Science cluster via the ‘Describing X-Ray Spectroscopy Data for Cross-Domain Use’ (CDIF-4-XAS) project¹⁹⁰, funded under the 1st OSCARS Open Call. In October 2024, CDIF-4-XAS released its second result deliverable, CDIF-4-XAS: Mappings from Community Standards to CDIF¹⁹¹, which provides mappings of two XAS standards (XDI and NXAS) to CDIF, thereby assisting interoperability and reuse, and demonstrating their implementation in Galaxy workflows. In addition, CDIF is also being implemented, refined and extended in the Climate-Adapt4EOSC and FAIR4DDE projects¹⁹², as well as in several other European and international projects beyond EOSC. CODATA continues to maintain the CDIF WG and its subgroups to coordinate and support these efforts.

OStrails¹⁹³, while being counted among domain-agnostic INFRAEOSC projects, can also be considered as a domain-specific project due to its five thematic pilots¹⁹⁴ related to the ESFRI Science Cluster:

- Physics;
- Social Science;
- Social Sciences and Humanities;
- Biodiversity;
- Language Resources;
- Astronomy and particle physics.

¹⁸⁶ oscars-project.eu/news/2nd-oscars-open-call-concluded-12-projects-selected (accessed 2025.11.10)

¹⁸⁷ David, R., Hienola, A., Schmidt-Tremmel, F., van der Lek, I., Nentwich, M., Bodera Sempere, J., Kalaitzi, V., Guerrieri, G., Wolff-Boenisch, B., Guezennec, C., Draščić, M., & Vipavc Brvar, I. (2025). D3.2 Competence Centres concepts and activities (pre)existing in EOSC. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17549887>

¹⁸⁸ The Cross-Domain Interoperability Framework is now presented as the CDIF Book: cross-domain-interoperability-framework.github.io/cdifbook/introduction.html

¹⁸⁹ worldfair-project.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁹⁰ oscars-project.eu/projects/cdif-4-xas-describing-x-ray-spectroscopy-data-cross-domain-use (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁹¹ Richard, S., Gregory, A., Austin, P., Görzig, H., Hodson, S., Krahl, R., Kubin, M., Liborio, L., Nieva de la Hidalga, A., Lungley, D., Tykhonov, V., & Rizzolo, F. (2025). CDIF-4-XAS: Mappings from Community Standards to CDIF. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17421917> (accessed 2025.11.20)

¹⁹² codata.org/initiatives/making-data-work/cdif/cdif-at-idw2025/

¹⁹³ ostrails.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.13)

¹⁹⁴ ostrails.eu/thematic-pilots (accessed 2025.11.13)

As already mentioned in section 3.1.2.1, there are numerous initiatives collaborating with INFRAEOSC projects which are important to track. They can be found in the INFRAEOSC description of call for proposals. Here are some examples of those domain-specific initiatives:

- ESFRI ¹⁹⁵, its WGs and TFs¹⁹⁶ which focus on thematic areas such as Energy, Environment, Health & Food, Physical Science & Engineering and Social Sciences & Humanities;.
- European Data Spaces¹⁹⁷ with fourteen domain specific data spaces such as in Agriculture, Cultural Heritage, Energy, Finance, Green Deal and Health;
- Health related platforms and data spaces such as the Medical Informatics Platform¹⁹⁸ and the European Health Data Space European data space¹⁹⁹;
- Climate and earth related platforms or services such as the Disaster Risk Management Knowledge Center Risk Data Hub²⁰⁰, the European Climate Adaptation Platform ²⁰¹, the Copernicus Services²⁰² and the GEOSS Portal²⁰³.

Finally, the Climate Adapt resource catalogue²⁰⁴ is also a rich source for discovering services, thematic features and tools tailored to domain-specific areas related to a Climate-Resilient Europe, such as water management, disaster risk management, health, biodiversity protection and more.

3.2.2.2. EOSC Federation domain-specific Nodes

EOSC Federation is described and discussed in the above section 3.1.2.4. Several of the enrolled initiatives in EOSC Nodes are domain-specific and are indicating the respective ESFR scientific domains²⁰⁵:

- BBMRI-ERIC, for Health and Food;
- CERN, for Physical Science & Engineering;
- Data Terra, for Environment;
- EUDAT, for Data, Computing and Digital;
- PaNOSC, for Physical Sciences & Engineering;
- Life Science Research, for Health & Food;
- Blue-Could, for Environment

¹⁹⁵ www.esfri.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

¹⁹⁶ www.esfri.eu/working-groups (accessed 2025.11.19)

¹⁹⁷ digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/policies/data-spaces (accessed 2025.11.19)

¹⁹⁸ [/www.ebrains.eu/tools/medical-informatics-platform](http://www.ebrains.eu/tools/medical-informatics-platform)(accessed 2025.11.19)

¹⁹⁹ health.ec.europa.eu/ehealth-digital-health-and-care/european-health-data-space-regulation-ehds_en (accessed 2025.11.19)

²⁰⁰ drmkc.jrc.ec.europa.eu/risk-data-hub (accessed 2025.11.19)

²⁰¹ www.eea.europa.eu/themes/climate/european-climate-adaptation-platform-climate-adapt (accessed 2025.11.19)

²⁰² www.copernicus.eu/en/copernicus-services (accessed 2025.11.19)

²⁰³ www.geoportal.org/ (accessed 2025.11.19)

²⁰⁴ climate-adapt.eea.europa.eu/en/data-and-downloads?size=n_20_n&filters%5B0%5D%5Bfield%5D=issued.date&filters%5B0%5D%5Bvalues%5D%5B0%5D=All%20time&filters%5B0%5D%5Btype%5D=any&filters%5B1%5D%5Bfield%5D=language&filters%5B1%5D%5Bvalues%5D%5B0%5D=en&filters%5B1%5D%5Btype%5D=any&sort-field=issued.date&sort-direction=desc (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁰⁵ eosc.eu/wp-content/uploads/2025/10/EOSC-A_GA11_20251010_Slide-deck.pdf (accessed 2025.11.11)

3.2.3. Within global initiatives

In this section, we explore the domain-specific activities among the global initiatives and report its updates and trends.

Three main global initiatives explored are:

- **CODATA**: plays an internationally recognised role to advance OS and the FAIR principles and has brought significant expertise to major policy and strategy documents (e.g. Turning FAIR into Reality, and the UNESCO Recommendation on OS). Among the ways CODATA aims to achieve these priorities are through Task Groups (TGs) and Working Groups (WGs).
 - *CODATA Task Groups (TGs)*: are groups of scientists, researchers and data experts who work together on a specific problem or theme to advance the state of data management.
 - *CODATA Working Groups (WGs)*: differ from TGs in that they are set up by the CODATA Executive Committee and are expected to complete their activity within a set period of not normally more than two years.
- **Global Open Science Cloud (GOSC)**: aims to encourage cooperation, alignment and ultimately interoperability among a number of OS clouds or common initiatives.
 - *GOSC use cases*: refer to pilot scenarios to show how a federated OS cloud can support global research collaboration and interoperability
- **United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO)**: is a “specialised agency of the United Nations with the aim of promoting world peace and security through international cooperation”²⁰⁶ and has published a set of principles and practices to guide what OS is and how to make scientific research accessible to everyone²⁰⁷
 - *UNESCO Priority areas*: refer to context of OS implementation.

Summary of domain-specific efforts among the global initiatives:

- Domain-specific activities of the global initiatives focus on real-world challenges, such as the EOSC ecosystem and security aspects related to each disciplinary domain, such as sensitive data for the health domain or crisis data related for the natural disaster domain.
- Sharing issues are commonly addressed by harmonising data (CODATA FAIR-DRR TG), reproducibility (GOSC Open reproducible raw diffraction data for access in pandemics case study) and through UNESCO platform that gather multiple resources providing RDM guidance and user responsible training material.
- This trend appears to show efforts towards harmonised systems and responsible users. CODATA, GOSC and UNESCO are relevant and informative sources for continuing the OS landscape analysis.

²⁰⁶[ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization \(UNESCO\)#:~:text=United%20Nations%20Educational%2C%20Scientific%20and%20Cultural%20Organization%20\(UNESCO\),-Glossary%3AUnited%20Nations](https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php?title=Glossary:United_Nations_Educational_Scientific_and_Cultural_Organization_(UNESCO)#:~:text=United%20Nations%20Educational%2C%20Scientific%20and%20Cultural%20Organization%20(UNESCO),-Glossary%3AUnited%20Nations)

²⁰⁷ <https://www.unesco.org/en/open-science/about> (accessed 2025.11.14)

3.2.3.1. CODATA domain-specific groups

The new 2025-2027 CODATA TGs include 2 out of 8 initiatives that are domain specific²⁰⁸: FAIR Data for Disaster Risk Research (FAIR-DRR) (continuing TG), which aims to continue harmonising and supporting FAIR-compliant data ecosystems to strengthen coherence with global efforts such as the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction²⁰⁹, the Sustainable Development Goals and more; and Geographical Indications Environment & Sustainability (GIES) (continuing TG), which aims to continue focusing on the free transfer of GIES technology and to provide principles and guidelines for GIES implementation and ethical development²¹⁰.

None of the CODATA WGs cover domain-specific areas²¹¹.

3.2.3.2. Global Open Science Cloud domain-specific case studies

Unlike the GOSC WGs, the GOSC case studies focus on domain-specific or cross-domain²¹² and remain unchanged since 2023.

Domains and research areas include:

- Incoherent scatter radar data fusion and computation;
- Biodiversity and ecology information platform;
- SDG-13 climate change and natural disasters;
- Sensitive data federation analysis model in population health; and
- Open reproducible raw diffraction data for access in pandemics.

3.2.3.3. UNESCO domain-specific priority areas

The UNESCO OS knowledge sharing platforms aims to connect users with open platforms focusing on UNESCO priority areas which are domain-specific, such as Biodiversity, Climate Change, Disaster Risk Reduction, Geology and Earth Science, Ocean and Water²¹³.

All digital resources collected to promote learning about OS and to support teaching in line with the 2021 UNESCO Recommendation on OS are accessible in the UNESCO catalogue²¹⁴. These include domain-specific resources, such as the “Data Management Plans for Open Social Science – Guidance for Researchers”²¹⁵ or the “ROSiE Training Materials for Responsible OS: Health and Life Sciences”²¹⁶.

²⁰⁸ codata.org/events/general-assembly/general-assembly-2025/ (accessed 2025.11.15)

²⁰⁹ www.undrr.org/implementing-sendai-framework/what-sendai-framework (accessed 2025.11.20)

²¹⁰ https://drive.google.com/file/d/1UwouYL8jVbU1nhVFr1ILhwxUki0_ViOA/view (accessed 2025.11.15)

²¹¹ codata.org/initiatives/working-groups/ (accessed 2025.11.15)

²¹² goscloud.net/cases (accessed 2025.11.15)

²¹³ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/knowledge-sharing (accessed 2025.11.15)

²¹⁴ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/capacity-building-index (accessed 2025.11.14)

²¹⁵ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/data-management-plans-open-social-science-guidance-researchers?hub=686 (accessed 2025.11.14)

²¹⁶ www.unesco.org/en/open-science/rosie-training-materials-responsible-open-science-health-and-life-science-s?hub=686 (accessed 2025.11.14)

In addition to offering a rich ecosystem of OS resources, the UNESCO catalogue also brings together numerous organisations engaged in OS initiatives.

3.3. Development in the regional and national approaches

3.3.1. Within RDA community

RDA recognises the importance of engaging national and regional members into its activities.

The MS10²¹⁷ report, published in June 2025, indicates a total 34 regions engaged with RDA Foundation²¹⁸. However, at the time of writing, there are a total of 33 regional groups²¹⁹ and 9 global groups²²⁰ within the RDA community. The decrease in the number of regional groups may reflect changes in the categorisation of RDA groups that have taken place since June 2025, and were also noticed in the section 3.2.1.1.

Table 9. Number of RDA groups by regions.

	Europe ²²¹	South America ²²²	Australia ²²³	North America ²²⁴	Asia ²²⁵
Number of RDA groups	22	2	1	3	1

Table 9 shows the number of RDA regional groups available by region. Follow the RDA groups by region:

- Asia region includes only one Asia group;
- Australia region includes Australasia group;
- Europe region includes Austria, Bulgaria, Croatia, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Ireland, Italy, Lithuania, Netherlands, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Slovenia, South Eastern Europe, Spain and Sweden groups;
- North America region includes Canada and the United States, as well as the Americas group, and the RDA North America regional group;
- South America region includes Costa Rica and Brazil groups.

²¹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

²¹⁸ www.rd-alliance.org/membership/regional-membership/ (accessed 2025.06.03)

²¹⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_group_type=regional-group (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=global (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²¹ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=europe (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²² www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=south-america (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²³ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=australia (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=north-america (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/group-directory/?_region=asia (accessed 2025.11.20)

While the RDA webpage states that there are a total of 33 regional groups, the actual count reveals only 29 groups, with missing groups such as Ecuador²²⁶ or Educação Em Pauta²²⁷ or Indonesia²²⁸. Additional inconsistencies, such as the reduced number of RDA regional groups in Europe and South America also indicate that categorisation changes have occurred and highlight the importance of regularly updating the landscape analysis.

RDA also organises various region-specific webinars to promote knowledge exchange within and across regions²²⁹ such as:

- RDA in the Baltics webinar (March 2025),
- RDA in Poland webinar (June 2025),
- RDA in Ireland webinar (September 2025)
- RDA in Denmark webinar (October 2025).

In addition, the first RDA in Europe Summit²³⁰ was held in Paris in November 2025, in collaboration with RDA France and CNRS, to discuss RDA's role and priorities within the border European landscape. The results from the upcoming D3.6²³¹ were presented at the RDA Europe Summit, highlighting the close relationship between RDA WG and EOSC ecosystem activities.

RDA community also focuses on national OS policies, notably through the recent published report: *"The Value of RDA for Policy Series - Advancing Community-Led Impact on Science Policies"*²³² and the upcoming D3.6²³³, which aligns RDA WG outputs with European National OS strategies.

Finally, RDA TIGER has published in June 2025 D2.3: Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs²³⁴, which concretely describe how RDA TIGER activities are being implemented within the European community and European National Networks.

Summary of geographic specific efforts among the RDA community

- National and regional activities are approaches taken into account by the RDA community, which is making considerable efforts to support these initiatives.

²²⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-ecuador/activity (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²⁷ rd-alliance.org/groups/educacao-em-pauta-1405109052/activity (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²⁸ rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-in-indonesia/activity (accessed 2025.11.20)

²²⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/news/rda-europes-regional-webinar-series/,
www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-in-denmark-webinar/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²³⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/events/rda-europe-annual-summit/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²³¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

²³² Clare, C., Allison, R., Genova, F., Hanahoe, H., Knazook, E., O'Connor, R., & Kurapati, S. (2025). The Value of RDA for Policy Series - Advancing Community-Led Impact on Science Policies. Zenodo.
<https://doi.org/10.15497/RDA00137>

²³³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

²³⁴ Halbert, G., Lehtsalu, L., & Delipalta, A. (2025). RDA TIGER D2.3: Report on the progress of European national network engagement in RDA TIGER WGs. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15775225>

- The RDA TIGER project significantly supports these efforts by analysing and mapping the implementation of the RDA community and its outputs within national and regional initiatives.

3.3.2. Within EOSC ecosystem

At the time of writing, the EOSC Federation includes six National EOSC Nodes²³⁵ which are Finland²³⁶, Germany²³⁷, Italy²³⁸, Poland²³⁹, Slovakia²⁴⁰ and Netherlands²⁴¹.

Regarding the EOSC Federation and its Nodes, it has been established that a more direct and high-level liaison with many countries is required. One of the actions taken to achieve this is to organise National Tripartite Events (NTEs). According to EOSC Focus, since the start of the project in 2022, 33 NTEs have been organised, targeting 28 countries and involving more than 4000 participants²⁴². Among the NTE held in 2025 were:

- the Poland NTE (March 2025)²⁴³;
- Croatia NTE (May 2025)²⁴⁴;
- France NTE (September 2025)²⁴⁵;
- Slovenia NTE (November 2025)²⁴⁶.

All NTEs and other EOSC events are available on the EOSC events webpage²⁴⁷.

In collaboration with EOSC Focus project²⁴⁸, the EOSC-A Country page^{249,250} was developed to provide a detailed overview of national developments in key OS components such as policies, institutional frameworks, and key stakeholders. Since the MS10²⁵¹ report in June 2025, no new OS policies have been released. However, EOSC Focus published in November 2025 the report “D2.2-Engagement

²³⁵ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²³⁶ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-finland/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²³⁷ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-germany/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²³⁸ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-italy/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²³⁹ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-poland/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴⁰ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-slovakia/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴¹ eosc.eu/building-the-eosc-federation/eosc-node-surf/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴² Caetano, I., Galica, N., Hasani-Mavriqi, I., Märkälä, A., de Jong, F., Reichmann, S., Sanchez-Santana, B., Schröder-Pander, F., & Vins, D. (2025). EOSC Focus - Deliverable 2.2 - Engagement Activities Review. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17572839>

²⁴³ eosc.eu/events/national-tripartite-event-poland-3/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴⁴ eosc.eu/events/national-tripartite-event-czech-republic-2/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴⁵ eosc.eu/events/national-tripartite-event-france-3/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴⁶ eosc.eu/events/national-tripartite-event-slovenia-3/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴⁷ eosc.eu/events/category/eosc-nte/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴⁸ eosc.eu/eu-project/eosc-focus-project/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁴⁹ eosc.eu/news/stay-up-to-date-on-open-science-developments-with-eosc-a-country-pages/ (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁵⁰ eosc.eu/tripartite-collaboration/#countries (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁵¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

*Activities Review*²⁵², listing project's partners have been responsible for coordinating activities across five specific regions: Central Europe; Eastern Europe, Nordic countries, Southern Europe, and Western Europe.

Summary of geographic-specific efforts among EOSC ecosystem:

- The National Tripartite Events (NTEs) of EOSC-A are important events that bring together organisations, institutions, representatives of the national research community, and other relevant stakeholders. Discussions range from the latest developments in EOSC services, as well as good practices, collaboration challenges, and much more.
- This type of event has been taken up by other initiatives, such as the HE-funded project FAIR-IMPACT with its national roadshows²⁵³, demonstrating their strong impact and the importance of organising national events to foster discussions within a given region.
- EOSC's geographic efforts bring forward high-potential stakeholders and initiatives, which represent a rich source of information for OS landscape analysis.

3.3.3. Within Global Organisations

3.3.3.1. CODATA national committees

A National Member is a scientific academy, research council, scientific institution, or association of such institutions, which has activities in research data. Each National Member is expected to establish a national committee²⁵⁴ for maintaining liaison between its national activities and the CODATA secretariat.

Since the last update in June 2025, the number of CODATA national committees remain unchanged. Currently, CODATA hosts eighteen national committees, including: Austria, Australia, Botswana, Canada, Chile, China, Finland, India, Israel, Japan, Kenya, Korea, Mongolia, New Zealand, South Africa, Taiwan (Taipei), Ukraine, United Kingdom, and the United States of America.

3.3.3.2. Research Software Engineers national and multinational groups

Since the last update in June 2025, the number of national/multinational Research Software Engineers (RSE) association groups²⁵⁵ has increased from nine to thirteen. This includes: Africa; Asia; Australia & New Zealand; Belgium; Canada; Chile; France; Germany; Netherlands; Nordic countries (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway, Sweden); Switzerland; United Kingdom; and United States.

²⁵² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17572839>

²⁵³ fair-impact.eu/events/national-roadshows (accessed 2025.11.20)

²⁵⁴ codata.org/membership/national-members/ (accessed 2025.11.10)

²⁵⁵ researchsoftware.org/assoc.html (accessed 2025.11.10)

The RSECon25²⁵⁶, which took place in September 2025, offers an overview of all RSE and related associations from all around the world.

3.3.3.3. *Global Open Science Cloud national initiative*

GOSC has developed a vast network of regional partnerships. First, thought its use cases; namely the two GOSC regional use cases: Mongolia²⁵⁷ and African²⁵⁸ Sustainable Development Community. Moreover, GOSC has expanded its regional and international presence through workshops and training sessions such as the GOSC SDG-13 workshop in Bangkok²⁵⁹, GOSC training series in Mongolia²⁶⁰ and Kenya²⁶¹ or GOSC Pan-Africa virtual series²⁶².

Additionally, GOSC initiative has established a partnership with the Chinese Academy of Sciences, running until 2026, to strengthen connectivity and interoperability between different research platforms, under an international pilot project entitled ‘GOSC Initiative’. Strategic partnerships with CODATA and other worldwide OS information infrastructures have also been developed to expand the global network of the GOSC Initiative. Indeed, efforts have been reinforced through the endorsement of the CODATA TGs on Open Science Cloud Service XI metadata (see section 3.1.3). This aims to create a metadata schema that is both human-understandable and machine-readable, and also integrate various research resources within the OS framework²⁶³.

In September 2025, the International Symposium on Open Science Clouds (ISOSC)²⁶⁴ was held. Partners included GOSC, CSTCloud, CODATA, Center of Big Data for Sustainable Development Goals,²⁶⁵ and Institute of Space Earth Sciences, with one of the objectives is to advance the GOSC Node initiatives²⁶⁶. The launch of the GOSC Nodes was announced. This aims to create decentralised hubs for OS, scaling nodes from local to global contexts and proposing measurable indicators to evaluate their impact on research and solutions.

²⁵⁶ rsecon25.society-rse.org/global-rse-communities/ (accessed 2025.11.10)

²⁵⁷ goscloud.net/openCommunityDetail/67246664bcb4d3419fc0d1be (accessed 2025.11.26)

²⁵⁸ goscloud.net/openCommunityDetail/65a888da65c655c2727dcab5 (accessed 2025.11.26)

²⁵⁹ goscloud.net/viewNewsDetail/65af7fd2a35789f4a153e42d (accessed 2025.11.26)

²⁶⁰ www.cstcloud.net/training/165.jhtml (accessed 2025.11.26)

²⁶¹ goscloud.net/viewNewsDetail/6641aaa4080982113e18c3cd

²⁶² www.cstcloud.net/training/155.jhtml (accessed 2025.11.26)

²⁶³ www.cstcloud.net/news/203.jhtml (accessed 2025.11.26)

²⁶⁴ english.cnica.cas.cn/nws/events/202508/t20250821_1051190.html (accessed 2025.11.26)

²⁶⁵ www.cbac.ac.cn/en/ (accessed 2025.11.26)

²⁶⁶ council.science/events/international-symposium-on-open-science-clouds-2025/ (accessed 2025.11.26)

Finally, GOSC's regional and international collaborations are also achieved through open-access publications such as the 2021 "The Global Open Science Cloud Landscape"²⁶⁷ or the latest version v1.2 of The "Global Open Science Cloud: Vision and Initial Successes"²⁶⁸, published in 2024.

Summary of geographic-specific efforts among global ecosystems:

All global initiatives have national and regional groups, which seems important for anchoring their activities in concrete situations and contexts.

3.3.4. Other regional initiatives and networks

As noted in previous D3.1²⁶⁹, D3.4²⁷⁰ and MS10²⁷¹ landscape reports, it is important to keep an eye on the many diverse global networks. This not only focuses on OS-related activities, but also on data sharing and management through e-infrastructures, as well as closely related areas involving data handling, such as data science training and academic collaborations.

The following section provides a brief overview of the different initiatives collected throughout the iterations of the Landscape Analysis. This includes OS-related initiatives such as:

- The Network Research and Education Networks (NRENs), which provide universities and research institutes high-quality network connectivity;
- Platforms or services which focus on data sharing or data management;
- Training or educational initiatives which aim at fostering data science knowledge and skills, all categorised according to their region of impact.

A set dataset compiling all the initiatives by region analysed are available and attached to the report²⁷².

3.3.4.1. Africa

National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) aims to "provide advanced information technology and communications services for connecting academic institutions to each other's

²⁶⁷ Yin Chen, Jianhui Li, Simon Hodson, Mark Dietrich, Tiziana Ferrari, Lili Zhang, Ane Persic, Geoffrey Boulton, Hussein Sherief, Sarah Jones, Corina Pascu, Ingemar Häggström, Xinna Yue, Junyi Wang, Eric Yen, Chenzhou Cui, Guido Lemoine, Kerstin Lehnert, Happy Sithole, ... Manish Parashar. (2021). The Global Open Science Cloud Landscape. EGI Conference 2020, Virtual. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5720674>

²⁶⁸ Yin Chen, Lili Zhang, Jianhui Li, Simon Hodson, Paul F. Uhler, Xueting Li, Hana Pergl, Ingemar Haagstrom, Xinan Yue, Junyi Wang, Xiaoli Zhang, John R Helliwell, Genji Kurisu, Joe Miller, Yingchao Piao, Monthip Sriratana, Gensuo Jia, Bapon Fakhruddin, Zhang Ying, ... Haiming Zhang. (2024). The Global Open Science Cloud: Vision and Initial Successes (1.2). Zenodo. doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8296516

²⁶⁹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

²⁷⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017310>

²⁷¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

²⁷² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034188>

networks, and to each other's resources, both nationally and globally.”²⁷³ In Africa, aside from each country NRENs, there are two alliances of these networks and are UbuntuNet²⁷⁴ Alliance, West and Central African Research and Education Network (WACREN)²⁷⁵ and Arab States Research and Education Network (ASREN)²⁷⁶, respectively connecting Eastern and Southern Africa; West and Central Africa and the Arab states.

Regarding platforms and services initiatives in Africa, we've identified nineteen of them. We are not able to study all of them in detail, we will analyse only those that seem most relevant and have recent developments. Among these is the Data Science Without Borders (DSWB)²⁷⁷, launched in 2024 for a three year period. DSWB recently published its Annual General Meeting²⁷⁸, highlighting the importance of structured mentorship, harmonised training efforts, and improved resource allocation to ensure sustainable growth and meaningful impact in leveraging AI/ML for healthcare advancements. The INSPIRE²⁷⁹ project, a multi-year, multi-partner and multi-project initiative, coordinated by African Population and Health Research Center (APHRC), has extended its scope of action by expanding its network to West and Southern Africa. In October 2025, these three initiatives: DSWB, INSPIRE and APHRC, participated in the International Data Week (IDW)²⁸⁰ in Brisbane and shared a common conviction: “data must always return home”²⁸¹, underscoring the importance of ensuring continuity between data provenance and data processing to maintain their quality and sustainability.

Regarding training initiatives on data science in Africa, we have identified only three of them: Association of African Universities²⁸², the Digital Hub for Open Research²⁸³ and the Regional Universities Forum for Capacity Building in Agriculture²⁸⁴. However, several of the African's platforms and services initiatives also offer training such as eLwazi²⁸⁵, H3Africa²⁸⁶ and INSPIRE²⁸⁷.

²⁷³ *The Role and Status of National Research and Education Networks (NRENs) in Africa*. 2017. World Bank Education

documents.worldbank.org/en/publication/documents-reports/documentdetail/233231488314835003 (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁷⁴ www.ubuntunet.net/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁷⁵ www.wacren.net/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁷⁶ www.asrenorg.net/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁷⁷ dswb.africa/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁷⁸ dswb.africa/reports/dswb-annual-general-meeting-2025-report/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁷⁹ inspiredata.africa/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁸⁰ idw2025.org/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁸¹ codata.org/blog/2025/11/18/data-without-borders-reflections-from-international-data-week-2025-brisbane/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁸² aau.org/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁸³ www.templetonworldcharity.org/projects-resources/project-database/33195 (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁸⁴ www.ruforum.org/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁸⁵ elwazi.org/training (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁸⁶ h3africa.org/index.php/resource/training/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁸⁷ inspiredata.africa/blog/training-and-capacity-building-needs-in-african-hdss-sites/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

While the call to strengthen the resilience of African institutions is widely shared by multiple initiatives, partnerships with regions beyond the African continent are maintained, and in some cases, reinforced. EU-African partnerships through the Africa-Europe Investment Package of the Global Gateway²⁸⁸ or the Research Infrastructures (RIs) call for proposal, such as the ‘Strengthen the bilateral cooperation on research infrastructures with Africa call²⁸⁹, has been extended to European Research Council (ERC) calls. This extension of HE and African Academy of Sciences partnership with the ERC will allow African researchers to temporarily join teams led by ERC grantees²⁹⁰. These collaborations are directly linked to political dimension, notably following the Trump administration’s policy of cutting development aids which consequently have strengthened European-African partnership.

3.3.4.2. Australasia

In Australasia region, we’ve identified two NRENs: the Australia's National Research and Education Network (AARNET)²⁹¹ and Research Education Advanced Network New Zealand (REANNZ)²⁹².

Regarding the platforms and services offered in the region, there is a strong partnership between Australia and New Zealand through the Australasian eResearch Organisations²⁹³. Aera supports the Research in higher education between the two countries, as well as the AusTrakka²⁹⁴ a platform developed in response to the COVID pandemic. The Australian Research Data Commons (ARDC)²⁹⁵ is an Australia-focused platform that serves as a research data infrastructure facility, offering multiple services to researchers. Other platforms or research infrastructures are available in the Research Infrastructure Connected²⁹⁶ which aims to connect researchers and innovators with Australia's national research infrastructure supported by National Research Infrastructure for Australia.

Regarding data science training and education, we have identified two national initiatives: the Skills and Workforce Development programme²⁹⁷ which supports various training programmes and is backed by the ARDC, and the New Zealand Data stewardship toolkit²⁹⁸, both providing free training in data science. Building on its experience, the ARDC has been organising National Digital Research

²⁸⁸ international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/global-gateway/initiatives-sub-saharan-africa_en (accessed 2025.11.25)

²⁸⁹ ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/HORIZON-INFRA-2024-DEV-01-02 (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁹⁰ sciencebusiness.net/news/r-d-funding/international-news/post-trump-african-science-pivots-new-partners (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁹¹ www.aarnet.edu.au/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁹² www.reannz.co.nz/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁹³ <https://aero.edu.au/> (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁹⁴ <https://austrakka.net/>

²⁹⁵ ardc.edu.au/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁹⁶ riconnected.org.au/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁹⁷ ardc.edu.au/program/skills-and-workforce-development/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

²⁹⁸ www.data.govt.nz/toolkit/data-stewardship/data-stewardship-toolkit (accessed 2025.11.21)

Skills Summit since 2019²⁹⁹, and recently published: Ten Simple rules for training by research for researchers in a rapidly evolving workforce³⁰⁰ to support the short-format training (SFT). This approach provides an efficient way to meet the demands of a fast-evolving workforce.

3.3.4.3. Asia

There are more than fifteen NRENs in Asia, along with additional networks such as, the Asia Pacific Advanced Networks³⁰¹, which connected the Asian region with the Pacific and provides extensive connectivity across this vast area; Trans Eurasia Information Network³⁰² and Central Asian Research and Education Network³⁰³.

Over the three years of Landscape Analysis iterations, we identified eight platforms and services supporting data sharing practices and policies, including the China Science and Technology Cloud which has already been described in the section 3.3.5 Global Open Science Cloud national initiative. Two of them are domain-specific initiatives such as the Polar Environment Data Science Center³⁰⁴ of the Joint Support-Center for Data Science Research of the Japan Research Organization of Information and Systems which aims to promote the opening and sharing scientific data obtained by research activities in polar regions, as well as eResearch South East Asia³⁰⁵ created during the COVID period, which seeks to strengthen connection between South East Asian researchers and research support provided in Australia, in partnership with ARDC, RSE-AUNZ, AARNET. The Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN)³⁰⁶ focuses not only on strengthening partnerships with Asian countries³⁰⁷ but also on establishing a legal status and institutional framework for its ten ASEAN member states: Brunei Darussalam, Cambodia, Indonesia, Myanmar, Lao PDR, Malaysia, Philippines, Timor-Leste, Singapore and Thailand. The Malaysia Open Science Platform³⁰⁸ is a national initiative from the Ministry of Science, Technology and Innovation to develop a trusted platform enabling accessibility and sharing of research data in alignment with national priorities and international best practices.

In the Asian region, we have not identified any training or educational networks initiatives in data science that specifically address data management and sharing practices. However, there is a notable development of university and national initiatives focusing on data repositories and especially on data management plans (DMPs), such as the the DMP FAIRER developed by Nanyang Technological University in Singapore, which aims to integrate the CARE principles into FAIR principles by adding an

²⁹⁹ ardc.edu.au/event/ardc-digital-research-skills-summit-2025/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁰⁰ doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1013408

³⁰¹ www.apan.net/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁰² www.tein.asia/sub/?mc=2010 (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁰³ www.caren.geant.org/Project/Background.html (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁰⁴ pedsc.rois.ac.jp/en/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁰⁵ www.ersea.org/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁰⁶ asean.org/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁰⁷ asean.org/about-us/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁰⁸ www.akademisains.gov.my/mosp/about/what-is-malaysia-open-science-platform/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

Ethical and Responsible dimensions (FAIR-ER), the depositor lab³⁰⁹ developed by Academia Sinica, with some funding from Taiwan's National Science and Technology Council; the Japan GakuNin RDM³¹⁰ which supports research teams by managing and sharing valuable data in one place; and the DataOn repository³¹¹ developed by the Korea Institute of Science and Technology Information.

As previously mentioned in the African region section, several of the organisation highlighted in this section participated in IDW2025 in Brisbane, and through a joint session³¹², they identified shared concerns as well as key issues, such as empowering the global data community for impact, equity and inclusion. The session also highlighted the importance of infrastructure to support local data-intensive research to facilitate its integration into a global dimension. However, in contrast to the African region, tEU-Sino partnerships, such as the EuroHub4Sino project³¹³ which aims to build a virtual European Info Platform on Contemporary China, are threatened with the recent announcement of the Chinese entities to decline participation to the Health, Civil Security and Society and Digital Industry and Space cluster of the HE work programme³¹⁴.

3.3.4.4. Europe

In Europe, we have identified more than forty NRENs, such as the French National Telecommunications Network for Technology, Education and Research³¹⁵, the Danish e-infrastructure Consortium³¹⁶, SURF³¹⁷ in the Netherlands, SWITCH³¹⁸ and in Switzerland. To our knowledge, two alliances of NRENs exist in the European region, one between five Nordic countries³¹⁹ (Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Norway and Sweden) and the other one the GEANT³²⁰ collaboration of European NRENs .

We have listed more than twenty of platforms that support data discovery and sharing, and most of which come from EOSC roadmap catalogue³²¹. Several of them stem from national initiatives such as Research Data Gouv³²² inaugurated by the French Minister of Higher Education and Research; the Dutch national centre of expertise and repository for research data called Data Archiving and

³⁰⁹ <https://lab.depositor.io/> (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹⁰ <https://support.rdm.nii.ac.jp/en/about/> (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹¹ dataon.kisti.re.kr/intro/intro01.do#a (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹² scidatacon.org/event/9/contributions/64/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹³ ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/projects-details/43108390/101131737 (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹⁴ www.researchprofessionalnews.com/rr-news-europe-horizon-2020-2025-11-eu-moves-to-bar-china-from-parts-of-horizon-europe/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹⁵ www.renater.fr/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹⁶ www.deic.dk (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹⁷ www.surf.nl/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹⁸ www.switch.ch/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³¹⁹ nordu.net/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²⁰ resources.geant.org/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/NEW-GEANT-Membership-map-March-25.pdf (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²¹ https://eosc.eu/eosc-about/eosc-macro-roadmap/?_mrm_catalogue=use-case (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²² recherche.data.gouv.fr/fr (accessed 2025.11.21)

Networked Services (DANS); and Nationale Forschungsdateninfrastruktur (NFDI) organised into consortia, including the Base4NFDI which develops basic services for the NFDI³²³. There are also pan-national initiatives, such as:

- OpenAIRE³²⁴, an infrastructure to support European research while also strengthening national capacity-building through its network and its National Open Access Desks^{325,326} that help to coordinate national efforts to align pan-European OS objectives;
- Council for National Open Science Coordination³²⁷, a network of national OS coordinators in the European region which aim to enhance OS policy alignment across countries.

As with data sharing services and platforms in the European region, there are national-level initiatives dedicated to training and education in data science. These include the Dutch Data Steward Interest Group³²⁸; the Italian Data Steward Community³²⁹; the Irish Data Stewardship Network³³⁰, and the OS Competence Network – Data Stewards Poland³³¹. Pan-national initiatives also exist, through collaboration with neighbouring countries, such as for the Nordic e-Infrastructure Collaboration and its FAIR data stewards course³³², open to Nordic and Baltic residents. European coordination of actions and the framework of data sharing skills and education can also take place through various HE projects such as:

- Skills4EOSC³³³ and its Competence Center Networks³³⁴;
- European Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence (EVERSE) project³³⁵ which aims at building a European quality network specifically for research software,
- Cluster Open Science Competence Centre³³⁶ of the OSCARS. an HE-funded project which aims to foster research excellence through training and knowledge transfer.

3.3.4.5. South America

In South America, we identified more than fifteen NRENs along one alliance called RedClara³³⁷ which interconnects eleven Latin American countries: Argentina, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Mexico, Paraguay and Uruguay; and to Europe via the GEANT Association.

³²³ www.nfdi.de/base4nfdi/?lang=en (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²⁴ www.openaire.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²⁵ www.openaire.eu/contact-noads (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²⁶ www.openaire.eu/noad-activities (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²⁷ conosc.org/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²⁸ tdcc.nl/dsig/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³²⁹ www.cids.it (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³⁰ www.ircdl.ie/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³¹ eosc.gov.pl/en/usecase/open-science-competence-network-data-steward-pl/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³² neic.no/fairdatastewardscourse/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³³ skills4eosc.eu/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³⁴ www.skills4eosc.eu/network/competence-centres (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³⁵ everse.software/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³⁶ oscars-project.eu/clusters-open-science-competence-centres (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³⁷ www.redclara.net/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

We have identified only two platforms with data sharing services: La Referencia³³⁸ and the Chilean Data Observatory³³⁹, and one partnership network, called EU-Latin America and Caribbean (EU-LAC) Global Gateway³⁴⁰. Global Gateway stands for sustainable and trusted connection across the world by supporting partnership in specific areas³⁴¹ such as digital, education and research, health, transport and climate and energy. Four digital projects are supported in LAC region³⁴² and two on the education and research area³⁴³.

The EU-LAC Digital Alliance³⁴⁴, also part of the Global Gateway, is a policy and human-centric initiative which aims to build a bilateral digital cooperation, such as building regional Copernicus data centers or extend BELLA cable programme, part of the RedClara NREN. This large alliance was launched in 2023 and brings more than twenty LAC countries: Argentina, Bahamas, Barbados, Belize, Brazil, Chile, Colombia, Costa Rica, the Dominican Republic, Ecuador, El Salvador, Guatemala, Honduras, Jamaica, Mexico, Panama, Paraguay, Peru, Suriname, Trinidad and Tobago, Uruguay and Guyana³⁴⁵.

Although we haven't identified any training or educational networks focused on data science in the region, the transfer of knowledge and skills appears to take place mainly through ongoing projects, such as the workshops of the ResInfra Plus project.³⁴⁶

3.3.4.6. North America

We identified four NRENs in the North America region such as CANARIE network³⁴⁷ in Canada, Internet2³⁴⁸ and ESnet network³⁴⁹ in United State and the National Regional Networks consortium called Quilt³⁵⁰.

³³⁸ www.lareferencia.info/en/nodes (accessed 2025.11.21)

³³⁹ dataobservatory.net/ (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁴⁰ international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/global-gateway/initiatives-latin-america-and-caribbean_en (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁴¹ international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/global-gateway/global-gateway-overview_en (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁴² international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/global-gateway/digital_en?f%5B0%5D=local_ndici_regions_regions%3A132#oe-list-page-filters-anchor (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁴³ international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/global-gateway/education-and-research_en?f%5B0%5D=local_ndici_regions_regions%3A132#oe-list-page-filters-anchor (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁴⁴ international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/policies/global-gateway/eu-latin-america-and-caribbean-digital-alliance_en (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁴⁵ https://www.eeas.europa.eu/eeas/eu-latin-america-and-caribbean-digital-alliance_en (accessed 2025.11.21)

³⁴⁶ resinfra-eulac.eu/events/join-us-for-an-online-workshop-on-research-infrastructures/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁴⁷ www.canarie.ca/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁴⁸ www.internet2.edu/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁴⁹ www.es.net/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵⁰ www.thequilt.net/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

To identify platforms with data sharing services in that region, we looked at national funding and institutions like the US National Institute of Standards and Technology³⁵¹, National Institutes of Health (NIH)³⁵², National Science Foundation³⁵³ and the Canadian Digital Research Alliance of Canada³⁵⁴. Through these, we are able to identify multiple initiatives such as the NIH Cloud Platform Interoperability³⁵⁵, NIH Data Science³⁵⁶ or NIH Data Commons³⁵⁷. Moreover, by looking at University initiatives we are also able to identify data services and platforms such as the Dataverse repository³⁵⁸ supported by Harvard University. Finally, in partnership between the Pervasive Technology Institute at Indiana University and the RDA-US³⁵⁹, the TIGRUS programme³⁶⁰ was launched in 2023 and worked closely with RDA TIGER and assists the RDA-US community in tackling data challenges specific to the US and amplifying results that are achieved through RDA in collaboration efforts with the international RDA community.

We identified several North American training and education programmes in data science, such as NASA Open Science 101 Modules³⁶¹, mentioned in the UNESCO's WG on OS Capability Building (see section 3.1.4.4 UNESCO domain-agnostic working groups). However, courses are also offered by national institutions, university services, or platforms, such as those mentioned above:

- NIH Data Science Training³⁶²
- NIH New Models of Data Stewardship (NMDS) program³⁶³ which aims to support research efforts to enhance biomedical discovery by piloting new digital data management strategies;
- Dataverse training³⁶⁴,

or by national institutions such as the Canadian Alliance's Explora³⁶⁵, a Canadian digital research infrastructure training.

³⁵¹ www.nist.gov/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵² www.nih.gov/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵³ www.nsf.gov/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵⁴ www.alliancecan.ca/en (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵⁵ www.ncpi-acc.org/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵⁶ datascience.nih.gov/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵⁷ cde.nlm.nih.gov/home (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵⁸ support.dataverse.harvard.edu/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁵⁹ rda-us.org/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁶⁰ www.cni.org/pbs/rda-us-pilots-the-targeted-international-working-groups-us-tigrus-program (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁶¹ openscience101.org/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁶² datascience.nih.gov/twice/training-resources (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁶³ commonfund.nih.gov/data (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁶⁴ support.dataverse.harvard.edu/calendar/upcoming (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁶⁵ explora.alliancecan.ca/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

4. Contribution of the RDA Knowledge Base³⁶⁶

Since the publication of the D3.4 Landscape report in October 2024, the RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB)³⁶⁷, developed by the RDA TIGER WP4 Outputs Service, has made significant progress. Three consecutive workshops were held for RDA members in May 2025 to promote the RDA-KB and gather feedback. The first workshop³⁶⁸ was a beta launch of the RDA-KB, introducing an early version of its suite of services, while the second and third³⁶⁹ workshops were particularly directed at RDA WGs. These featured more in-depth demonstration of RDA-KB features, use-cases for RDA WGs, hands-on testing, and opportunities to provide feedback and questions. Following further development using the feedback gathered from the aforementioned events, the RDA-KB was launched on October 6th³⁷⁰. In the following sections, the four main components of the RDA-KB and their applications for landscape monitoring are discussed in brief. For additional information, see “Getting to Know the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Knowledge Base”,³⁷¹ and the official documentation for the Knowledge Base.³⁷²

4.1. RDA Graph

The RDA-KB now features a complete catalogue of RDA outputs and supporting materials, as well as the bibliographic data about associated authors, working/interest groups, and institutions, among others. The data is continuously synchronised via an API connection with the RDA website, which was developed in collaboration with RDA and their web developer, Marameo. Considerable effort went into consolidating, disambiguating, and deduplicating these records, which had been created organically over time. The resulting database is referred to as the RDA Graph.

The RDA Graph features associated RDA (associated) vocabularies, many of which were purpose-built by WP4.³⁷³ These include RDA-specific vocabularies on e.g. RDA Pathways, group status, and membership roles, stakeholder groups; RDM-related vocabularies on e.g. licenses, domains/disciplines, and principles; as well as vocabularies created by RDA WGs and other organisations, such as The Global Open Research Commons (GORC) vocabulary.³⁷⁴

³⁶⁶ Previously referred to as the ‘Maintenance Platform.’ For additional information about the RDA Knowledge Base and its status in the final months of the project, as well as further detail about the name change, see D4.3: Final report on the lessons learned from providing Support Services, at DOI:

<http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17762711>

³⁶⁷ kb-rda.org/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁶⁸ www.rd-alliance.org/event/rda-tiger-knowledge-base-beta-launch/ (accessed 2025.05.27)

³⁶⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/event/rda-knowledge-base-hands-on-feedback-session-1/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁷⁰ A recording of the launch webinar can be found on:

<https://www.rd-alliance.org/news/welcome-to-the-rda-knowledge-base/> (accessed 2025.11.30)

³⁷¹ Sharma, C. J. M., Hugo, W., & Saldner, S. (2025). Getting to Know the Research Data Alliance (RDA) Knowledge Base (1.0.0). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17882751>

³⁷² Knowledge Base documentation available at DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737222>

³⁷³ Hugo, W., Polimeno, A., Saldner, S., Laurens, T. (2025). RDA Knowledge Base: Tag Lists, Registries, and Vocabularies [Data set] Zenodo. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17771724>. Also on kb-rda.org

³⁷⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/gorc-international-model-wg/outputs/ (accessed 2025.11.30)

Resources entered into the RDA Graph are linked to the above-mentioned vocabularies as well as to each other. This greatly improves the findability, harmonisation, and usefulness of these resources. Landscape monitoring provides a good use case for these features, as they make it easier to identify resources by e.g. topic, discipline, or associated contributors. Results from landscape analyses can also be integrated into the RDA Graph, further enriching the data, and making their findings available to other RDA users.

4.2. RDA Discovery

4.2.1. Search and discovery functions

RDA Discovery is a web-interface through which users can access and search entries from the RDA Graph.³⁷⁵ It features dashboard- and list-types views of resources, which can be filtered by various vocabularies such as topic, WG, or year, as well as free-text queries. The Dashboard interface is highly configurable and interactive, and facilitates searching and filtering using e.g. geographical, chronological, or graph-like representations. Dashboard views can also be saved and shared with other users, without requiring a user account. The List view provides a detailed view of the same results that are displayed in the Dashboard view, with all associated metadata, including abstract, URLs, and associated authors and WG.

RDA Discovery allows users to easily search and access the entire RDA corpus, to identify items of interest, and to associate them with various RDA (-related) vocabularies. These features make it easier for users to carry out a landscape analysis of RDA-related outputs, assets, groups, and more. The search results and dashboard/list views can easily be shared with other users (e.g. working in the same WG), to facilitate collaboration. The web-frame that underlies the RDA Discovery is highly configurable, and can on request, potentially be customised by RDA WGs to demonstrate the results of their landscape analysis.³⁷⁶

³⁷⁵ Accessible via: rda-kb.org

³⁷⁶ For additional technical information about RDA Discovery, and other components of the Knowledge Base, see the associated documentation at DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737222>

Figure 2: Dashboard view of the RDA Discovery Application

4.2.2. Support documentation and helpdesk

The RDA Discovery interface also features a ‘Support Materials Drawer’ which can be accessed in the bottom-right corner of the RDA-KB website, under ‘Support’. This features a catalogue of support materials for RDA users, including:

- **Group Guidance and Support:** e.g. guidelines for RDA members participating in WGs, including RDA rules & procedures, best practices, and publication instructions.
- **Technical documentation and instructions:** information and recommendations on the use of RDA-KB components
- **Templates, Systems, and Tools:** e.g. templates for output reports, recommended metadata schemas, and vocabulary lists
- **Additional resources:** RDA (-related) resources that are considered useful to RDA members, e.g. standards development recommendations from HSBooster.

These resources include guidelines and recommendations useful to WG members generally, including resources particularly useful for landscape analyses, such as related advice on landscape analysis publication, and which templates to use.

The RDA-KB also includes a Helpdesk, available from the bottom-right corner of the RDA-KB website, under ‘Help’. This allows users to create tickets for RDA TIGER personnel relating to bug fixes, questions, feature requests, and so on.

4.3. RDA Annotator

The RDA Annotator³⁷⁷ is a browser extension and service of the RDA-KB that allows RDA users to annotate text-snippets from any web-based resource with descriptions and RDA-related metadata and vocabularies. RDA groups spend a lot of time and effort searching the landscape for materials, which often need to be read and analysed in detail. Aside from what is included in the final output, the results of these laborious landscape analyses do not tend to be reused by others. This is what motivates the Annotator. The Annotator lets users save useful materials found in the process of landscape analyses carried out by WGs, provide them with descriptions and link them to RDA vocabularies, thereby making them findable and reusable to other users via the RDA-KB.

In short, the Annotator can annotate any piece of text that the user selects on the web. The Annotator can then apply keywords, descriptions/notes, and various RDA-related vocabularies to the annotation, which contextualises and categorises the content. Annotations made using the Annotator are then passed to the RDA Graph, which can then be accessed by any user via RDA Discovery. This allows RDA users to capture useful information at a very granular level which may not make it into published reports, allowing other users to find, contextualise and use such information in the future. Annotations are visible to other users as highlighted in the text being browsed, Annotations are associated with a user’s ORCID account. This allows other users to identify who has produced an annotation, and to browse all annotations that they themselves have created. The Annotator is highly customisable, and can be fitted with additional vocabularies, which can then be toggled on or off by the individual user as needed. This functionality makes it particularly useful for landscape analysis efforts.

The RDA Annotator is a browser extension available for Chromium- and Firefox -based browsers, that builds on the open-source code from the annotation tool [Hypothesis.is](https://hypothesis.is).³⁷⁸ The RDA Annotator is available for download via the RDA-KB website. The browser extension will be available from the

³⁷⁷ kb-rda.org/annotator (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁷⁸ For technical documentation, see DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17737222>;

For user guidelines, including installation, and use, see Laurens, T., Hugo, W., Saldner, S. (2025). RDA Annotator: Guidelines Instructions for installing and using the RDA Annotator. Zenodo <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17772540>. Also on kb-rda.org.

Google Chrome Web Store, which will facilitate installation and updates.³⁷⁹ WP4 is currently working on promoting its uptake among RDA Users through webinars³⁸⁰, and to work with select RDA WGs to identify use cases and gather feedback.

The aims and structure of the deliverable

Figure 3: RDA Annotator in action

4.4. RDA Publisher

The RDA Publisher³⁸¹ application assists with the publication of RDA resources (outputs, supplementary materials, or any other resource) to both Zenodo and the RDA Graph. The approach has several advantages, including the ability to accommodate more than one metadata schema depending on the type content, and to link to any number of LOD-type vocabularies and registries to better contextualise the resources. This flexibility provides added future proofing, since it may eventually become necessary to publish RDA outputs elsewhere than Zenodo. For example, groups may develop new formal or specific standards that they may want to be preserved, even if these aren't available on Zenodo.

The RDA Publisher can be configured for multiple deposit targets. In the case of RDA, one might want to deposit copies of a resource to Zenodo, to a long-term preservation platform, and possibly the RDA website in one automated execution. By using controlled vocabularies and preserving consistent

³⁷⁹ The extension is currently under review by the Chrome Web Store, and should be available soon.

³⁸⁰ www.rd-alliance.org/news/welcome-to-the-rda-knowledge-base/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁸¹ kb-rda.org/publisher

metadata across resources, the curated workflow provided by the Publisher reduces the effort required for publishing outputs, including the duplication of deposits, and makes deposits traceable and locatable. These outputs are useful to RDA users in general, but may have particular applications for landscape analysis efforts, e.g. should authors want to include particular metadata along with their publication.

Currently, the Publisher is ready to be implemented on a technical level, but policies surrounding the implementation, including the relation between the RDA website and Publisher.

5. Lessons learned

The lessons learned from three years of WP3 activities are detailed in three sub-parts. The first two concern the two main activities of WP3, which are the Landscape Awareness service for RDA TIGER-supported working groups and the Landscape Monitoring. The last part showcases the significant contribution of the RDA KB in highlighting the resources collected throughout the different landscape activities.

5.1. Landscape Awareness service

At the beginning of the RDA TIGER project, Landscape Awareness service reported a very low number of requests from RDA WGs (D3.2 report)³⁸². One of the identified causes of this low rate of demand was the overlap between the engagement component of the Landscape & Engagement service and other RDA TIGER services, especially the Facilitation service (D3.3 report)³⁸³. Indeed, as a facilitator is assigned to assist a WG with engagement alone, and since each WG's engagement strategy and activities are linked to its overall objectives, it is more common for the individual assigned to the WG by the RDA TIGER Facilitation service to provide engagement support by communicating invitations related to the group's activities, thereby reducing the demand for Landscape Awareness.

To address the overlap between services and promote the Landscape Awareness service, a more detailed description of the service was communicated within the various RDA WGs supported by the RDA TIGER service. This promotional campaign helped highlight the potential impact of this service engagement within the WGs. Moreover, the absence of published reports of the requested landscape analysis also appears to have been a barrier to the service's visibility.

Once the WP3 Landscape Awareness service began to experience an increase in demand, we realised that the service was not only requested by WGs at the early stages of their development but also in the more mature stages. Indeed, within the Landscape Awareness service, the landscape analysis requested by RDA WGs are very specific to each request, but are generally aimed at helping these

³⁸² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10444701>

³⁸³ O'Connor, R., Papadopoulou, A., Lehtsalu, L., Halbert, G., & Delipalta, A. (2024). RDA TIGER D3.3 Engagement Services Status. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14534784>

groups gain a better understanding of initiatives related to their topic. While most groups already carry out this work and are well acquainted with initiatives within the EOSC ecosystem, the added value of the service provided by external and knowledgeable support for the group is considerable, as thus at any stage of the WG development.

Two RDA TIGER supported WGs approached the WP3 Landscape Awareness service after the WGs had started working. RDA/WDS TRUST Principles Outreach and Adoption³⁸⁴ WG asked for support to identify potential respondents for the survey that they had developed. Alignment of multilingual vocabularies in the Social Sciences and Humanities³⁸⁵ WG asked for support to re-start the group's activities after they experienced a period of limited member engagement. In both cases, the group co-chairs with the support of their RDA TIGER Facilitators, defined target groups that they wished to reach. They then asked the Landscape service to identify relevant organisations or individuals. For both groups, the Landscape service helped them reach new audiences and potential members in the middle of the WG life cycle. In the case of the FAIR Mappings³⁸⁶ WG, the requested Landscape service was slightly different by mainly focusing on enriching their mapping use cases in order to identify potential gaps or new ways of doing and sharing mappings.

There are also RDA WGs that requested support at the early stage of their development. These were the Small Uncrewed Aircraft and Autonomous Platforms Data (SUAV)³⁸⁷ WG, Reproducibility Checklist³⁸⁸ WG and Ethics in Agricultural Data³⁸⁹ WG. The added-value of the Landscape service was mainly to identify potential partnerships and relevant stakeholders to be involved in their activities. This included collecting information through organised surveys or speaker series to discuss specific topics related to the WGs' scope. These collected initiatives and stakeholders are also intended to be used as a contact list to gather feedback on the WG's outputs, ensuring that their recommendations or work are well integrated into the relevant domain of impact.

Thus, the Landscape Awareness service requested by the RDA WGs can clearly enhance the dynamics, activities and impact of the WG, highlighting the added value and importance of conducting this work through external and knowledgeable stakeholders capable of providing an exhaustive and unbiased search on the WG's topic.

³⁸⁴ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rdawds-trust-principles-outreach-and-adoption-working-group/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁸⁵ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/alignment-of-multilingual-vocabularies-in-the-social-sciences-and-humanities-wg/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁸⁶ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/fair-mappings-wg/activity/

³⁸⁷ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/small-uncrewed-aircraft-and-autonomous-platforms-data-working-group/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁸⁸ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/rda-reproducibility-checklist-working-group/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁸⁹ www.rd-alliance.org/groups/ethics-in-agricultural-ag-data-wg/activity/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

5.2. Landscape monitoring

During the different iterations of the Landscape monitoring (reports D3.1³⁹⁰, D3.4³⁹¹, MS10³⁹² and the current one D3.5), we analysed the development and trends of the pre-selected initiatives and were able to identify new initiatives and activities related to the OS ecosystem. Since the research and innovation landscape is evolving rapidly, these iterations are important to keep current with new trends and scope.

However, we encountered difficulties in ensuring year-to-year follow-up of initiatives, mainly due to changes in the indicators used, within or in between the initiatives. For example, within the RDA community, certain WGs categories have been modified, which distorts the analysis of their evolution. In addition, indicators vary from one initiative to another, complicating the overall assessment of trends and the dynamics of the OS landscape. Furthermore, the introduction of new initiatives between different iterations also has an impact on the overall structure of the reports, which may make them more difficult for readers to follow.

A more in-depth analysis of each collected initiative is something that should be conducted regularly in order to provide clear, direct, and relevant information that connects with the topic of each WG. This will help WGs to find their place in the OS ecosystem, as well as identify specific projects or recommendations to follow based on the topic they are addressing. One of the most relevant examples is the upcoming RDA TIGER D3.6 “Landscape analysis on the value of RDA Outputs to EOSC”³⁹³, which aligns the activities of RDA WGs with the EOSC ecosystem, thereby enabling each WG to recognise and identify its place within the European ecosystem.

5.3. RDA KB contribution

The RDA Knowledge Base (RDA-KB) is a powerful tool. It not only allows the integration of resources collected throughout the WP3 activities within the RDA community, enhancing their visibility and usability through a consolidated database known as the RDA Graph, but also enables the formalisation and integration of OS vocabularies, particularly EOSC, to more easily connect OS initiatives with the RDA community.

The external resources collected through the different WP3 activities - Landscape Awareness analysis for the WG and the various iterations of the OS Landscape monitoring - have significant potential to enhance the impact and activities of RDA WGs and the broader RDA community, particularly by integrating their work into the OS ecosystem and contributing to its development. These international initiatives identified will be integrated and made available in the Knowledge Base “Support Materials” drawer. Below is the list of collected resources coming from:

³⁹⁰ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8096612>

³⁹¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14017310>

³⁹² <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15774733>

³⁹³ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

- Landscape Awareness service³⁹⁴:
 - D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_WGs_Resources.
 - D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_Other
- Landscape monitoring³⁹⁵:
 - D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_Africa;
 - D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_Australasia;
 - D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_Asia;
 - D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_Europe;
 - D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_SouthAmerica;
 - D3.5-LandscapeAnalysis_NorthAmerica.

The RDA-KB also strives to connect the OS and EOSC ecosystem within the RDA community, notably through the annotation of relevant EOSC publications and the integration of EOSC vocabularies into the KB using the RDA Annotator.

Indeed, WP3 identified the relevant EOSC publications and sources that link them to the activities of RDA WGs, both within the framework of the OS landscape iteration and in the D3.6 report, which provides a concrete mapping of EOSC activities to RDA WG activities. The RDA KB has already annotated eleven EOSC-related documents in its catalogue³⁹⁶. The EOSC ecosystem vocabularies identified in the D3.6³⁹⁷ report have been formalized to allow their integration into the RDA KB. These EOSC-related vocabularies will then be implemented and connected to RDA WGs once D3.6 is finalised and submitted. The identified vocabularies are:

- EOSC-A Task Forces;
- EOSC Opportunity Area Expert (OEAG);
- SRIA challenges;
- SRIA priority areas;
- ERICs.

6. Conclusion and recommendations

The Landscape monitoring provides updates of the current OS initiatives and their evolution, allowing for monitoring of new directions and ambitions in the field. So, the methodology developed for the Landscape Analysis effectively highlights new trends and developments in the OS and data science ecosystem. It shows that the initiatives used for the analysis are relevant and appropriate for this exercise and can be applied in future iterations.

³⁹⁴ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034188>

³⁹⁵ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18034188>

³⁹⁶ Results from “EOSC” search in the annotation filter of the www.kb-rda.org/search

³⁹⁷ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17877370>

The WGs of RDA, CODATA, and ReSA, as well as EOSC projects and EOSC-A TFs, are valuable sources for identifying relatively new standards, best-practice recommendations and specifications to ensure OS compliance, support efficient data sharing, and manage infrastructures effectively, as well as for identifying new operational services. Because these groups generally operate over short periods, around two to three years, we recommend regularly monitoring their activities to stay up to date with their developments.

In contrast, initiatives focused on policy and strategic roadmapping, such as the EOSC SRIA, the UNESCO OS Recommendation, and GOSC WGs, provide long-term guidance and recommendations and therefore require less frequent monitoring to keep track of their evolution. Activities of these initiatives provide essential variables related to global challenges and still provide an important driver for pooling and standardising data.

Other important sources of OS information include in-person meetings or conferences, which offer key opportunities to track initiatives developments at different levels. For example, the IDW2025³⁹⁸ conference fostered the exchange of research knowledge, amplified voices on shared concerns, and highlighted new considerations. Another important event within the OS ecosystem is the EOSC Symposium³⁹⁹. It is considered the flagship annual event of the EOSC community by bringing together a wide range of stakeholders. Another key conference is the International Conference on Research Infrastructures (ICRI)⁴⁰⁰ which is part of a series of conferences funded by the European Commission. The next ICRI will be held in 2026 and will bring together key stakeholders to discuss challenges and emerging trends related to RIs in a global context.

The global political situation and ongoing conflicts⁴⁰¹ are influencing data sharing and OS directions. Over the past five years, new major challenges have emerged, profoundly altering OS practices. Indeed, the 2020 pandemic forced researchers to share data quickly; the release of ChatGPT in 2022 changed the way research is produced and processed; geopolitical conflicts, and interference have modified the framework for data sharing; and changes in political directives, along with certain scientific skepticism, have led to research initiatives such as the “Data Rescue” movement, alongside the emergence of Choose Europe for Science. To address these rapid changes, the mechanisms, scope, and framework for research data sharing need to be updated regularly

OS, and in a broad way, data science, are closely linked to technological innovations, such as LLMs, which evolved rapidly and transformed how research is done, measured and evaluated. Regular iterations of the landscape analysis are therefore essential. The arrival of new technologies, particularly LLMs in 2022⁴⁰², has significantly transformed the OS landscape. The effect of LLMs and

³⁹⁸ idw2025.org/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

³⁹⁹ eosc.eu/eosc-symposium-2025/ (accessed 2025.11.25)

⁴⁰⁰ cordis.europa.eu/project/id/101261024 (accessed 2025.11.25)

⁴⁰¹ en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Russo-Ukrainian_war (accessed 2025.11.25)

⁴⁰² en.wikipedia.org/wiki/ChatGPT (accessed 2025.11.25)

AI appear ambiguous: with on the one hand a huge demand for access to any and all text and data; on the other hand a chilling effect to a degree as distrust grows for how these data are used. Efforts have been made to strengthen data science literacy and training, notably through Short-Format Training (SFT)⁴⁰³, in order to keep up with new trends and innovations. Many initiatives have directly included a specific training section in their programmes.

New technologies also affect the reliability of research analyses and outputs, which has led to numerous initiatives aimed at improving and evaluating the security, responsibility, and reliability of shared data. The closer connection between research and policy is also being strengthened to ensure that the use of these technologies is framed within a legal context. Indeed, the policy aspects of OS and data sharing are further reinforced by climate and societal crises, such as interference and misinformation, which increases the focus on crisis data management.

It is also in this unstable political context that many organisations and stakeholders are calling for the support of local initiatives for responsible and resilient management of data-related activities. digital sovereignty and strategic autonomy. This could on the one hand speed up the development of regional infrastructures like EOSC, while also disrupting international cooperation. Thus, keeping track of upcoming regional, national, and global policy recommendations seems to be a good starting point for following the new directions and recommendations of OS, which will directly influence best practices in data sharing and management.

6.1. Recommendations

While we consider the coverage of the OS landscape to be relevant and sufficiently effective for tracking new trends and innovative initiatives, we are aware that it is heavily biased toward European and North American initiatives. One recommendation for improving for future landscape analyses will be to include initiatives beyond these regions, which are already partially covered in the Geographic section (see Section 3.3.5 National and Regional Initiatives and Networks). The advent of generative AI and its ability to quickly translate multiple languages will open access to these regions, and will significantly enhance knowledge of OS, data sharing and the associated practices.

WP3 recognised the importance of conducting multiple landscape analyses to maintain and promote an up-to-date integration of RDA WGs activities into the OS ecosystem. However some improvements can be made. First, the broader representation and formalisation of satellite initiatives surrounding the RDA WGs can be found in the group's case statements. Their integration into the RDA KB would definitely enhance the connectivity of RDA communities to external initiatives. Moreover, an in-depth analysis of the connectivity of the RDA community with OS and EOSC initiatives, like the one carried out in D3.6, represents a crucial and direct way to formalise the interconnection with the activities and efforts contributed by the RDA community. RDA KB is

⁴⁰³ Lovelace-Tozer M, Brown J, Clemens R, Greenhill K, Haseen F, Kingsley D, et al. (2025) Ten simple rules for training by researchers for researchers in a rapidly evolving workforce. *PLoS Comput Biol* 21(9): e1013408. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1013408>

currently working on implementing EOSC-related vocabularies into its catalogue, thereby foresting the implementation in this direction.

The experience of the Landscape Awareness service has shown that the nature and relevance of the resources collected depend on the needs of the groups. These needs evolve not only with their development stages but also with the evolution of their activities. To improve the adoption, visibility, and usability of these resources, the identification and integration mechanisms are being strengthened. The integration aligns with RDA TIGER services and, more specifically, with the RDA KB, contributing to the visibility and incorporation of external initiatives within each group. Another recommendation to improve the integration of the overall information collection would be to use crowdsourcing within the RDA community. This would significantly help identify precise and relevant connections, as well as potential partnerships between the RDA community and the relevant stakeholders of the OS ecosystem.

Thus, WP3 recognises the strong value of the landscape analysis service in collecting and rapidly connecting relevant OS-related initiatives to the RDA WGs. The continuation of this service appears desirable in the long term and is strongly encouraged. WP3 thus expresses its motivation in continuing to further develop this service in collaboration with the project partner organisations. One possible solution would be to produce an annual analysis covering all identified initiatives and linking them to RDA activities and WGs.

